

Plant diversity in old-growth woods: the case of the forest edges of the Favorita Park in Palermo (north-western Sicily, Italy)

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Abstract

This article presents the results of a study on plant diversity at different levels in residual forest stands, located in the historical Favorita Park in Palermo, Italy (established and named in 1799 by King Ferdinand IV of the House of Bourbon). These forest aspects have naturally evolved for over two centuries, under minimal conditions of anthropogenic disturbance (e.g. deforestation, fires, grazing activities, etc.). This is especially true in the area known as “Bosco Niscemi”, spread over about 8.5 hectares, in the centre of the park. Bosco Niscemi is characterized by the widespread presence of old trees, abundant necromass and litter. In this study, four different soil profiles were analysed, and classified as follows: (i) Solimovic Regosol (Arenic); (ii) Eutric Arenosol (Chromic); (iii) and (iv) Skeletic Regosol (Ochric). From a phytosociological point of view, four forest communities have been identified, two of which are described as new associations (*Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova and *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova). The species richness was also found to be noteworthy, with the co-occurrence of several taxa (phanerogams and cryptogams) that are of biogeographic interest or rare in Sicily, including: i) vascular flora (e.g. *Viburnum tinus* and *Arbutus unedo*, both very rare throughout the western sector of Sicily); ii) bryophytes [*Cryphaea heteromalla* (new record of a very rare species in Sicily) as well as *Hypnum cypressiforme* and *Leptodon smithii*, also never previously found at such low altitudes]; iii) lichens (e.g. *Bacidia rosella*, *Gyalecta derivata*, *Ramalina roesleri* and *Waynea stoechadiana*); iv) mushrooms (e.g. *Eichleriella leucophaea*, only known location in Italy). Based on the scientific documentation produced in this study, these woods can be reported as “old-growth forests” to be included in the “National Network” that has been recently established in Italy (Ministerial Decree of 23 June 2023). This area might serve as an ideal control for urban environmental studies, given its pristine ecological setting.

Keywords

Conservation of biological diversity, forest ecosystems, monumental trees, old woods, pristine ecosystems, *Quercetea ilicis*, rare species

Introduction

In recent years, research regarding what are known as “old growth forests” and understanding how their “free evolution” relates to the conservation of threatened diversity has become increasingly important, especially since this diversity is particularly sensitive to anthropogenic disturbances in the environment.

According to the UN Environment Programme’s definition “... an old-growth forest is a primary or secondary forest that has reached an age in which the species and structural attributes are comparable to senescent primary forests of the same type, such as to make it distinct as an ecosystem compared to younger woods” (UNEP 2001). Therefore, old growth forests are woody formations where human intervention has ceased for some time, character-

ized by a marked naturalness (richness in macro- and microfauna, vascular flora, mosses, macromycetes, lichens, etc.) and structural (presence of different layers of vegetation, dead wood, litter, etc.), ecological-functional and dynamic complexity. Identifying and studying these plant formations is important, especially to better enhance and protect this bio-ecological heritage and its structural heterogeneity by implementing appropriate protection and safeguarding actions and by applying adequate forest management measures. In recent years, this need has been reaffirmed by various international conventions, such as the “Pan-European Strategy for Biological and Landscape Diversity” which addresses this specific issue by emphasizing the main objectives of “ensuring the conservation of all forest typologies in Europe, primarily protecting the oldest [...], conserv[ing] the forest habitats of species that need extensive and undisturbed habitats”.

In Italy, an initial study aimed at identifying the old-growth wood types of national parks was published by Blasi et al. (2010), which was followed by some initiatives on a regional scale (Marchetti et al. 2012) and a number of other scientific studies (Burrascano et al. 2009; Frascaroli et al. 2016; Romagnoli et al. 2018; Guidotti et al. 2010). In recent years, some scientific surveys have also concerned Sicily (Badalamenti et al. 2018; Maetzke et al. 2017, Sferlazza et al. 2023), which mainly regarding the distribution, floristic-structural characteristics and the ecological functions of old growth woods fragments found on the island.

This paper illustrates the results of an investigation aimed at characterising some centuries-old forest stands located in Palermo’s Favorita park (north-western Sicily, Italy) from a phytosociological point of view and at analysing its valuable plant diversity. This historic urban park

was established and enclosed in 1799 by King Ferdinand IV of the House of Bourbon to create a game preserve and site for agricultural experimentation. Baptized as the “Real Tenuta della Favorita” after the sovereign’s other estate near Naples, it initially covered approximately 400 hectares. It serves as an important “green lung” close to the urban area, extending along a heterogeneous transect from the Palermo Plain to the detrital slopes of Mt. Pellegrino. Since 1995, it has been protected as part of the Mount Pellegrino Nature Reserve. Additionally, this study also aims to quantify the value of the reserve’s plant diversity, which has been preserved in the same ecosystems as a result of the aforementioned conservation and protection measures (e.g. significant frequency of ancient or “monumental” arboreal specimens and/or almost exclusive presence of rare taxa of vascular flora, bryophytes, lichens and fungi).

A further objective is to evaluate the possibility of proposing the entire Favorita site to be included among the “old growth woods” of Sicily, in order to implement the “National Network” that has recently been established in Italy by Ministerial Decree of 5 april 2023 – Ministry of Agriculture, of Food sovereignty and Forests (G.U.R.I. S.G. n. 138/2023).

Study area

The study area extends over an area of about 180 hectares within the former “Real Tenuta della Favorita”, at an altitude between approximately 50 and 200 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1). A historic topographical map of the park, drafted by Francesco Guttoso in 1856 (Fig. 2), is preserved in the “Giuseppe Pitrè” Ethnographic Museum in Palermo (Buffa et al. 1986). The document shows that the area known as the “Bosco

Figure 1. Study area (displayed in white), showing the delimitation of the following forest nuclei under investigation: *Quercus ilex* forest (in blue); maquis forest of *Phillyrea latifolia* with *Arbutus unedo* and *Viburnum tinus* (in green); maquis of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* with *Cercis siliquastrum* (in red); ombrophilous maquis of *Phillyrea latifolia* with *Teucrium flavum* and *Pistacia terebinthus* (in yellow).

Figure 2. Part of a historic topographic map of the former “Real Tenuta della Favorita”, drawn by Francesco Guttoso in 1856 and preserved at the Giuseppe Pittre Ethnographic Museum in Palermo (from Buffa et al. 1986, modified). In the central part, the area still occupied today by the “Bosco Niscemi” is clearly recognizable, divided into the 16 “squares” that characterize it.

Niscemi” has existed since then. It is located in the central part of the park and continues to be divided into the original 16 squares, each covering 4000 m². The total area, including the small roads that delimitate it as well as other “groves (K)” and hedgerows, covers a total of 6.4 hectares.

Historical background of the Favorita Park

Several previous studies (e.g., Buffa et al. 1986; Pirrone et al. 1990; Leone 2003; La Mantia 2004; Pirajno and Flaibani 2015; Sessa 2015) have provided useful insights into the history of the Favorita Park.

During the early 19th century, under Bourbon rule, the area that currently accommodates the Bosco Niscemi became a huge park whose design was inspired by the royal estates of continental Europe. A complex mosaic of hedgerows, ornamental and experimental gardens, tree allées and small wooded areas were created, mostly using native evergreen woody species.

Ferdinand IV of Bourbon, fleeing Napoleon’s troops during 1798 revolution in Naples, took refuge in Palermo, designating it as the new capital of the Kingdom. With the aim of creating recreational areas like those he enjoyed in Campania, he expropriated about 400 hectares of land, including part of the Piana dei Colli to the west, the Pantano di Mondello to the north, an area bordering the historic centre of Palermo to the south and the cliffs of Mt. Pellegrino to the east. After a brief return to Naples, Ferdinand returned to Palermo, where between 1806 and 1812 he further enriched the park, which was mostly used as a private hunting estate or devoted to agricultural experimentation. During this time, three main roads were built along with an intricate system of paths. At the same time, several neo-Gothic buildings were built or enlarged,

different ornamental and allegorical artefacts (e.g., statues, fountains) were installed, irrigation canals fed by aqueducts were created, and buildings for agricultural purposes (e.g., oil mills, wine cellars) were erected.

Little is known about the period between the sovereign’s death (1825) and 1860, when the Favorita passed to the House of Savoy as property of the Crown and was opened to the public. In 1877, the king ceded the park to the State. Part of the park was then converted to house military infrastructure (e.g., bunkers, embankments) and an airport (e.g., airship hangar and runway). In 1920, the king relinquished the usufruct of the park, leading to its division into four areas managed by different administrations. Once assigned to the municipality of Palermo, the park underwent further fragmentation and alteration during the following decades. Despite several public initiatives, such as the establishment of sports facilities between the 1930s and the 1970s, a process of slow but relentless decline began for the Favorita (Leone 2003).

Due to urban sprawl, the entire park and its agroforestry landscape have undergone gradual and continuous degradation and fragmentation over the past 60 years (Barbera et al. 2009). This, along with pedestrian barriers created by cutting arterial roads through the park to connect the city with the seaside village of Mondello has contributed to making the Favorita a no man’s land. In fact, for several decades, local ecosystems have developed almost untouched, disturbed only by the hectic and noisy comings and goings of citizens’ vehicles. During the 1980s, a wide area adjacent to Bosco Niscemi, originally part of the park, was allocated to host encampments of the nomadic Roma community of Palermo. Paradoxically, the long-lasting state of total abandonment of this sector of the park has preserved Bosco Niscemi to the present day, allowing local processes of undisturbed progressive succession to give this area levels of unpredictable naturalness

(Gianguzzi et al. 2017). Since 1995, the Favorita has been part of the “Monte Pellegrino” Nature Reserve, covering 1,050 hectares, established by the Sicilian administrative Region and managed by the NGO “Rangers d’Italia”.

Bioclimatology

The climatic data summarised in (Tables 1, 2) is taken from the thermo-pluviometric surveys of the Palermo Civil Engineering Hydrographic Service (Servizio Idrografico del Servizio Civile di Palermo; Ministero dei Lavori Pubblici 1926–1985, in Duro et al. 1996).

Table 1. Monthly and annual averages of maximum and minimum temperatures (in °C), daily ranges, and absolute maximum and minimum values recorded at the thermometric station of the Palermo Astronomical Observatory from 1926 to 1985 (Duro et al. 1996).

Palermo Astronomical Observatory (31 m a.s.l.)						
Month	Max	Min	Mean	Temp. range	Abs. Max.	Abs. Min.
January	15.7	7.8	11.8	7.9	30.4	-1.2
February	16.1	7.9	12.0	8.2	29.6	0.0
March	17.5	9.0	13.3	8.5	33.6	0.0
April	19.8	11.0	15.4	8.8	32.0	3.5
May	23.3	14.2	18.8	9.1	36.8	7.2
June	26.9	17.7	22.3	9.2	40.8	9.0
July	29.7	20.3	25.0	9.4	42.2	13.6
August	29.9	20.8	25.4	9.1	43.0	10.0
September	28.0	18.8	23.4	9.2	41.1	8.0
October	24.6	15.6	20.1	9.0	36.2	5.0
November	20.9	12.3	16.6	8.6	31.9	3.6
December	17.1	9.4	13.3	7.7	29.5	0.3
Year	22.5	13.7	18.1	8.7	43.0	-1.2

Table 2. Monthly and annual average values of rainfall (mm/m²) and number of rainy days (RD) recorded at the three rainfall stations in Palermo for the period 1926–1985 (Duro et al. 1996).

Month	Castelnuovo Institute (54 m a.s.l.)		Hydrographic Service (19 m a.s.l.)		Astronomical Observatory (31 m a.s.l.)	
	mm	RD	mm	RD	mm	RD
January	99.7	11	93.3	11	82.7	11
February	82.3	10	81.6	10	68.5	9
March	71.2	9	60.9	8	55.7	8
April	60.9	7	42.8	6	43.0	6
May	21.3	3	21.9	3	23.9	3
June	9.5	2	8.7	1	8.3	1
July	2.9	1	3.6	1	3.8	0
August	17.5	2	17.5	2	15.7	1
September	42.5	4	40.2	4	39.0	4
October	91.3	9	85.2	8	79.2	8
November	88.5	9	85.0	9	73.8	9
December	91.8	11	103.0	11	90.5	11
Year	679.4	78	643.8	73	584.1	71

The average daytime temperature of the area under study is 18.1 °C, whereas the average annual maximum and minimum values are 22.5 °C and 13.7 °C, respec-

tively. The coldest month is usually January (average minimum = 7.8 °C, average maximum 15.7 °C) while the hottest is August (average minimum = 20.8 °C, average maximum = 29.9 °C). The rainfall recordings carried out at three localities located in the Palermo Plain show annual averages of 679.4 mm (Castelnuovo Institute, located right on the edge of the Favorita Park), 643.8 mm (Hydrographic Service) and 584.1 mm (Astronomical observatory), with a number of rainy days of 78, 73 and 71, respectively.

Based on the bioclimatic classification criteria proposed by Rivas-Martínez (1996, 2008), the study area was found to be affected by a Mediterranean pluviseasonal oceanic bioclimate with a thermomediterranean thermotype and a dry-subhumid ombrotype.

Geolithology

From a geological point of view, the study area falls on the margins of the Sicilian segment of the Apennine-Maghrebian chain (Catalano et al. 1979, 2013). Local rock outcrops belong to what are known as the Panormide carbonate platform succession (Basilone 2018) and the “Cozzo-Lupo” stratigraphic-structural unit of the Lower Trias-Eocene (Abate et al. 1978). They are mainly composed of: a) Quaternary calcarenites (calcareous sands), which cover a large area of the Palermo Plain; b) scree and debris, flows with accumulations of red earth of colluvial origin, mainly concentrated along the slopes of the relief; c) compact limestones rich in fossils of the Pellegrino Formation (western slopes of Mt. Pellegrino. In particular, the Palermo Plain is made up of Pleistocene deposits (calcarenites and sandy clays) superimposed on impervious clay and marl soils of Numidic Flysch (Oligo-Miocene), which in turn rest on meso-cenozoic limestones (Abate et al. 1978; Catalano et al. 1979; Sparacio et al. 2017). Two aquifers are recognized on these substrates, one that is more superficial (on sandy clays and calcarenites) and the other found at a depth of around 100 m (in Mesozoic limestones), which are in turn separated discontinuously by impermeable Flysch (Calvi et al. 1998). These aquifers are fed by the waters that flow in the carbonate rocks of the Palermo Mts., resulting in humid and diversified ecological conditions within the Palermo Plain. The different edaphic characteristics of the study area have led to different potential vegetation, i.e. *Quercus ilex* forest (on the deepest, loamiest and most humified soils), and the maquis forest of *Phillyrea latifolia* (in marginal, more xeric and draining areas).

Materials and methods

Soil

The soils were characterized in accordance with the WRB guidelines (IUSS WG WRB, 2022), leading to their classification based on this system.

Vegetation analysis

The vegetation surveys of the forest nuclei were carried out in the period between April 2018 and June 2023. A total of 38 unpublished phytosociological relevés were carried out, according to the Zurich-Montpellier methodology (Braun-Blanquet 1964). For the syntaxonomic interpretation of the communities, the data were compared with those already available from previous literature (Brullo and Marcenò 1985; Buffa et al. 1986; Gianguzzi et al. 1996; Surano et al. 1996; Brullo et al. 2009; Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a, b, c). For the elaboration of synoptic tables including similar associations of the *Quercetea ilicis* class already described for Sicily (Appendix 1: Tables A1, A2), reference was made to Brullo et al. (2009) and other more recent papers (cited in the text). The nomenclature of the syntaxa follows the criteria of the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature (ICPN: Theurillat et al. 2021), whereas for the syntaxonomic classification of the communities, we referred to Mucina et al. (2016) and to Guarino and Pasta (2017).

Biodiversity analysis

To evaluate the role of “refuge habitat” of these forest ecosystems for the conservation of what’s referred to as “valuable” plant diversity (Gigante et al. 2016; Capotorti et al. 2020; Casavecchia et al. 2021), a census of the ancient trees (with localization and dendrometric survey) was performed.

For the classification of vascular plant species, reference was made to Pignatti et al. (2017–2019), while plant naming follows Bartolucci et al. (2018) and the updates available on the Portal to the Flora of Italy (2023). For bryophytes, their nomenclature follows Hodgetts et al. (2020); the specimens are preserved in the Herbarium Mediterraneum Panormitanum (PAL). The identification of lichens was performed using the the online keys published in “ITALIC, the Information System of the Italian Lichens, version 07” (see Nimis and Martellos 2020) and Smith et al. (2009), while their nomenclature follows Nimis (2024). For fungi, the nomenclature used refers to Ferraro et al. (2022), whereas the dried samples are preserved in the SAF Herbarium of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Sciences of the University of Palermo.

Results and discussion

Soil

We studied four soil profiles, the first two in the colluvium between the dunes (1) and on the back of the coastal sandy dune that covers the calcarenites (2), and the third and fourth on the debris of Mt. Pellegrino (4). The parent materials belong to the Quaternary complex of western Sicily, a calcarenitic-sandy-silty complex with mainly lithoid clasts, composed of calcite and siliceous rocks fragments and monocristalline quartz (sparitic grains and small amounts of bioclasts) (Zimbaro 2016).

The soils are classified respectively as: (1) Solimovic Regosol (Arenic) (Fig. 3); (2) Eutric Arenosol (Chromic); (3) and (4) Skeletic Regosol (Ochric) (IUSS WG WRB 2022). The average textural classification of these soils is 15% clay, 35% silt and 50% sand expressed as a percentage of the fine earth fraction. Average properties of the fine earth are: organic carbon $3.0 \pm 1.1\%$; pH 7.8 ± 0.6 ; BD soil bulk density $1.030 \pm 0.011 \text{ kg dm}^{-3}$.

Figure 3. Pachyamphi humus forms in the dune colluvium (site 1).

We used the European classification of humus forms (Zanella et al. 2011), based on the sequence and morphological characteristics, including evidence of biological activity, of organic and/or organomineral horizons observed and described in the field (Table 3). Our correlations between humus forms and soils are consistent with the cross-harmonization proposed by Vacca et al. (2018) for Mediterranean environments. In line with humus theory (Ponge 2003), the formation of humus primarily stems from nutrient availability and reflects the nutrient management approaches adopted by ecosystems. The presence of mull humus indicates systems rich in nutrients, showing

Table 3. Humus forms. Site locations in accordance with Figs 1, 3.

Site	Position	Humus	Horizon	Materials [*]	HC ² (%)	Depth (cm)
1	Dune colluvium	Pachyamphi	OLn/OF	l, tl, n, t, tt, twm	<10	1
			OH	twm, wdl, ztm, r	>70	2
			maA	r	<5	6+
2	Dune hump	Eumacroamphi	OLn	l, n, t, wm	<10	1
			OF/OH	t, tt, aad, r, wdl	>30	2
			saA	r	<5	4+
3	Talus slope	Eumull	OLn	l, n, t, wm	<10	1
			OF	tl, wdl, ztm, r	>30	2
			A	r	<5	5+
4	Talus slope	Eumull	OLn	l, n, t, wm	<9	1
			OF	tl, wdl, ztm, r	>28	2
			A	r	<4	4+

^{*} l = leaves; n = needles; t = twigs; wm = woody materials; pdl = partly decomposed litter; tl = transformed leaves; tn = needles; tt = transformed twigs; twm = transformed woody materials; wdl = well-decomposed litter; aad = aged animal droppings; ztm = zoogenically transformed material; r = roots; ² HC = humic component.

Figure 4. Schematic transect between the Palermo Plain (about 50 m a.s.l.) and Mt. Pellegrino (606 m a.s.l.), in which the geolithological substrates and the main vegetation aspects of the landscape are represented: (A) quaternary calcarenites [Solimovic Regosol (Arenic)]; (B) quaternary calcarenites [Eutric Arenosol (Chromic)]; (C) detrital-clastic materials [Skeletal Regosol (Ochric)]; (D) limestones and dolomites; (1) *Quercus ilex* forest (*Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini*); (2) maquis forest of *Phillyrea latifolia* with *Arbutus unedo* and *Viburnum tinus* (*Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova); (3) maquis of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* with *Cercis siliquastrum* (*Ruto chalepensis-Oleastretum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastrum*); (4) ombrophilous maquis of *Phillyrea latifolia* with *Teucrium flavum* (*Teucrio flavi-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova); (5) grassland vegetation (*Penniseto setacei-Hyparrhenietum hirtae*); (6) cliff vegetation (*Scabioso-Centauretum ucriae*); (7) maquis of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* with *Euphorbia bivonae* (*Ruto chalepensis-Oleastretum sylvestris* subass. *euphorbietosum bivonae*); (8) artificial plantations; (9) former cultivations (olive groves, etc.).

a rapid nutrient cycling strategy. It is assumed that because nutrient and organic carbon dynamics are interconnected and organic carbon turnover occurs swiftly, the substantial carbon reserves found are likely a consequence of high net primary ecosystem productivity. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that establishing a straightforward or essential link between these factors is challenging, even in the presence of fast nutrient cycling (Andreetta et al. 2011).

Forest vegetation

Four types of forest vegetation were identified in the study area (Fig. 4):

- Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* Brullo et Marcenò 1985 subass. *viburnetosum tini* Gianguzzi, Ilardi et Raimondo 1996;
- Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco;

- Ruto chalepensis-Oleetum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastrum* Gianguzzi et Bazan 2020;
- Teucrio flavi-Phillyreetum latifoliae* Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco.

***Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* Brullo et Marcenò 1985 subass. *viburnetosum tini* Gianguzzi, Ilardi et Raimondo 1996**

Holotypus. Rel. 10, table 5 in Gianguzzi et al. (1996).

Phytosociological data. Table 4, Appendix 1: Table A1 (column 3).

Diagnostic species. *Quercus ilex* (dom.), *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Clematis cirrhosa* and *Phillyrea latifolia*.

Short description. Dense, closed forest, with a clear dominance of *Quercus ilex*, of variable height between (5)7–14(20) m, in whose tree layer there are *Phillyrea latifolia* and sometimes *Fraxinus ornus* and *Celtis australis*. Other species include *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Arbutus unedo*,

Table 4. *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini*: rels. 1–10, Bosco Niscemi (14.11.2022, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 11–12, near the Forestry nursery (14.11.2022, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 13–14, near the Hercules Fountain (5.2.2013, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rel. 15, Villa d’Orleans (17.5.2014, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15			
Relevé number																		
Altitude (m a.s.l.)	55	54	54	53	54	47	46	45	44	45	63	64	64	63	50			
Slope (°)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	5			
Aspect	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	SE	W	W	W	W	W			
Area (m ²)	100	100	150	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	150	150	100			
Total cover (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100			
Life form	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100			
Tree cover (%)	50	45	50	45	45	50	50	50	45	45	50	50	50	60	25			
Shrub cover (%)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	70	30	10			
Herb cover (%)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			
Presence of deep litter (yes:+/no:-)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			
Presence of dead wood (yes:+/no:-)	15	20	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	9	10	15	15	10			
Seedlings (%)	9,0	7,0	8,0	7,2	7,5	7,2	7,2	15	11	10	7,1	7,0	14	10	18			
Average tree height (m)	16	13	13	13	15	15	14	18	13	15	15	14	17	16	20			
No. of species per relevé	Char. and diff. assoc.																	
P scap	<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	15	V	
P scap	<i>Quercus ilex</i> L. (seed.)	1	1	+	1	1	+	1	1	+	1	+	+	+	1	15	V	
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	2	3	3	2	1	2	1	1	+	1	1	1	2	1	15	V	
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	1	+	15	V	
P caesp	<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	3	2	3	4	4	2	3	2	3	4	3	3	1	3	1	15	V
P caesp	<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L. (seed.)	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	1	1	+	+	14	V	
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	14	V	
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	1	.	1	2	+	+	7	III	
P caesp	<i>Arbutus unedo</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	+	+	+	.	+	+	7	III	
P caesp	<i>Arbutus unedo</i> L.	2	1	2	1	1	+	6	II	
Char. all. Fraxino-Quercion ilicis (*) and Quercetalia ilicis																		
P scap	* <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.	1	2	.	.	.	2	+	2	3	.	2	7	III
P scap	* <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	.	+	.	.	+	1	.	.	7	III	
G rhiz	<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> L.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	+	5	II	
G rad	<i>Dioscorea communis</i> (L.) Caddick & Wilkin	+	.	+	+	+	+	6	II	
NP	<i>Rosa sempervirens</i> L.	1	.	+	.	.	1	.	5	II	
P caesp	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	1	.	.	.	+	+	3	I	
NP	* <i>Emerus major</i> Mill. subsp. <i>emeroides</i> (Boiss. & Spruner) Soldano & F. Conti	r	.	1	I	
G bulb	* <i>Cyclamen hederifolium</i> Aiton	+	1	I	
Char. Cl. Quercetea ilicis																		
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.	2	4	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	2	1	15	V	
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L. (seed.)	1	1	+	1	1	1	1	1	+	+	1	+	.	+	14	V	
G rhiz	<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> O. Targ.Tozz	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	+	2	1	1	1	2	2	14	V	
G rhiz	<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	+	+	+	1	.	+	+	1	+	+	10	IV	
P lian	<i>Rubia peregriana</i> L.	.	.	.	+	1	+	+	1	.	.	.	2	1	.	7	III	
P lian	<i>Hedera helix</i> L.	1	.	2	1	1	2	3	6	II
G rhiz	<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	+	.	.	1	.	1	.	.	2	1	1	6	II
P scap	<i>Celtis australis</i> L.	.	.	+	1	2	1	2	5	II
P caesp	<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	.	.	1	1	.	+	.	.	.	1	4	II
Ch frut	<i>Stachys major</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	.	.	.	+	+	+	4	II
H scap	<i>Pulicaria odora</i> (L.) Rchb.	+	.	.	+	+	3	I	
G bulb	<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	+	.	.	.	+	1	.	3	I	
H caesp	<i>Ampelodesmos mauritanicus</i> (Poir.) T.Durand & Schinz	1	+	.	2	I	
G rhiz	<i>Limodorum abortivum</i> (L.) Sw.	.	.	.	+	.	.	+	2	I	
P lian	<i>Hedera helix</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	.	.	.	2	I	
P caesp	<i>Anagyris foetida</i> L.	+	1	I	
NP	<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> L.	1	I	
NP	<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> L. (seed.)	1	I	
P caesp	<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L.	1	I	
Other species																		
H scap	<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.	1	1	+	.	1	1	+	+	+	+	2	3	4	1	1	14	V
G rhiz	<i>Arum italicum</i> Mill.	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	.	1	1	14	V
H bienn	<i>Smyrniolum olusatrum</i> L.	+	+	+	+	.	5	II	
H ros	<i>Polypodium cambricum</i> L.	.	.	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	4	II	
NP	<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i> Schott.	r	1	I	
G bulb	<i>Acis autumnalis</i> (L.) Sweet	+	1	I	
NP	<i>Cistus salvifolius</i> L.	+	.	.	.	1	I	
H scap	<i>Parietaria judaica</i> L.	1	1	I	
G rhiz	<i>Ruscus hypoglossum</i> L.	1	1	I	
H caesp	<i>Oloptum miliaceum</i> (L.) Röser & H.R.Hamasha	+	1	I	
T scap	<i>Urtica urens</i> L.	+	1	I	
P scap	<i>Phitolacca dioica</i> L.	+	1	I	

Average number of species for relevé

Figure 5. Average number of species per relevé in the main *Quercus ilex* associations described for the Sicilian territory (source data see Appendix 1: Table A1): the *Pistacio-Quercetum ilicis subass. viburnetosum tini*, is the community that presents the lowest value.

and some lianas (*Clematis cirrhosa*, *Rubia peregrina*, *Smilax aspera*, *Hedera helix* and *Asparagus acutifolius*), which are represented in the shrub layer. The herbaceous component of the undergrowth is poor (Fig. 5), essentially composed of some native sciaphilous-nitrophilous bulbous plants (*Acanthus mollis*, *Arisarum vulgare*, *Arum italicum*, *Smyrniolum olusatrum* etc.), as well as a rich frequency of seedlings of the dominant tree species (Fig. 6a–e).

Substrate/parent material and soil. Coastal Quaternary calcarenites on deep and evolved soils and with edaphic humidity (due to rising groundwater) are widespread in the internal part of the Palermo Plain. These soils are classified as Solimovic Regosol (Arenic) (IUSS WG WRB 2022).

Bioclimate. Mediterranean pluviseasonal oceanic thermomediterranean thermotype and dry-subhumid ombrotype.

Syntaxonomic notes. The *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* association has been described as a thermophilous holm oak forest in Sicily (Brullo and Marcenò 1985), linked to xeric alkaline substrates (marly, limestones, calcarenites, etc.). This forest association is rich in species of the order *Pistacio-Rhamnetalia alaterni* (Brullo and Marcenò 1985; Brullo et al. 2009). The subass. *viburnetosum tini* has been recognized in the calcarenites of the Palermo Plain (Gianguzzi et al. 1996, 2016a). In addition to the high frequency of *Pistacia lentiscus*, the following species are identified as differentials of the subassociation: a) *Viburnum tinus* [Steno-Mediterranean element with relict and fragmentary distribution (Pignatti 1982; Karlson et al. 2005), in Sicily known only in this area and in a few sites in the Sicani Mts. (Gianguzzi et al. 2016a) and Mt. Etna (Siracusa 1998; Brullo et al. 2009), etc.]; b) *Arbutus unedo* (acidophilous and calcifugal species, also quite rare in the basiphilous holm oak forests of the western sector of Sicily; Gianguzzi and La Mantia 2008); c) *Clematis cirrhosa*, a very common vine in this community.

Vegetation series. The community constitutes the best structured aspect of the “Climatophilous series north-west-

ern Sicilian, thermomediterranean from dry to subhumid, calcarenitic of *Quercus ilex* (with *Pistacia lentiscus* and *Viburnum tinus*)”: *Pistacio lentisci-Quercus ilicis viburnetosum tini* sigmetum (Brullo and Marcenò 1985; Gianguzzi et al. 1996; Brullo et al. 2009). On the more xeric and draining sandy-calcarenitic soils, located near the slopes of Mt. Pellegrino, it is replaced by the *Phillyrea latifolia* series of the *Viburno tini-Phillyrea latifoliae* sigmetum (whose more mature forest community is described in the following paragraph). Near watercourses – as in the case of the locality detected in Villa d’Orleans in Palermo, where the Kemonia Stream once flowed – it also finds contact with the hygrophilous series of *Salix pedicellata* of the *Ulmo canescentis-Salix pedicellatae* sigmetum (Gianguzzi et al. 2010, 2013, 2014).

Synchronology. The forest stands represent residual aspects linked to the coastal Quaternary calcarenites of the western sector of Sicily, where they were destroyed by man to make room for crops (citrus groves, orchards, and vegetable gardens) and urban areas. A further small nucleus of approximately 1 hectare was also located within Villa d’Orleans, in the urban area of Palermo (rel. 15 of Table 4). It has developed through free evolution over the last 150 years, although the undergrowth has undergone the removal of topsoil, litter and dead wood. There are also long-standing individuals of *Quercus ilex* here, reaching heights over 20 m.

Eunis code. G2.121 (Meso-Mediterranean *Quercus ilex* forests).

Natura 2000 code. 9340 (*Quercus ilex* and *Quercus rotundifolia* forests).

Number of nuclei and total coverage (in ha). 5 units (for 11,86 ha of coverage).

Viburno tini-Phillyreum latifoliae Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco

Holotypus. Rel. 3 in Table 5.

Phytosociological data. Table 5, Appendix 1: Table A2 (column 23).

Figure 6. (a) Overview of the forest core of the Bosco Niscemi; (b) old dead plant of *Quercus ilex* (photo from 2012); (c) detail of old trunk of *Arbutus unedo*; (d), (e) aspects of the *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass *viburnetosum tini*; (f) *Viburnum tinus*, a characteristic species of holm oak and *Phillyreetum* communities (respectively, *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass *viburnetosum tini* and *Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova), represented on the calcarenites, in different ecological contexts.

Table 5. *Viburno tini-Phillyreum latifoliae* ass. nova: rels. 1–4, Bosco Niscemi (22.2.2018, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 5–6, along the road beyond Villa Niscemi (06.2.2014, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 7–8, near the Hercules fountain (14.12.2017, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rel. 9, near the Rocche dello Schiavo (1.6.2023, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 10–11, near the Palazzina Cinese (1.6.2023, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella); rels. 10–12, Malvagno (1.6.2023, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella). Asterisk indicates the type relevé.

	1	2	3*	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Relevé number	1	2	3*	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Altitude (m a.s.l.)	55	55	47	48	61	60	62	63	65	60	62	58			
Slope (%)	3	3	3	3	2	5	4	5	4	1	2	2			
Aspect	S	S	S	S	NW										
Area (m ²)	100	100	100	100	100	100	150	100	100	100	100	100			
Life form															
Total cover (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100			
Tree cover (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100			
Herb cover (%)	10	15	20	15	20	20	30	20	10	20	10	10			
Presence of deep litter (yes:/no:-)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			
Presence of dead wood (yes:/no:-)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			
Average tree height (m)	6,5	7	7	6,5	6,5	6	6	6	7	8	6	10			
No. of species per relevé	14	11	12	11	14	10	16	13	13	12	14	12			
Char. and diff. assoc. and var. (°)															
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	12	V	
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L. (seed.)	1	1	1	1	1	1	+	1	1	1	1			
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	3	2	1	1	4	2	4	3	3	4	4	4	12	V
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L. (seed.)	2	2	+	2	1	1	+	2	2	1	2	1		
P caesp	<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	2	2	3	3	2	2	+	2	1	1	1	1	12	V
P caesp	<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	.	2	+	+	+	+	1	+	1	1		
P lian	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i> (L.) Druce	2	1	1	2	1	2	3	1	8	IV
Char. all. Oleo-Ceratonion and ord. Pistacio-Rhamnetalia alaterni															
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	1	3	2	1	3	2	2	3	4	3	3	2	12	V
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L. (seed.)	+	1	1	.	+	+	1	+	1	1	1	.		
P caesp	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	1	.	1	.	.	.	1	.	3	1	2	1	7	III
P caesp	<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	.	.	.	1	.	.	1	.	1	.	1	.	4	II
Ch frut	<i>Stachys major</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	+	.	1	1
Char. Cl. Quercetum ilicis															
P scap	<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	2	3	2	.	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	3	11	V
P scap	<i>Quercus ilex</i> L. (seed.)	+	+	.	.	.	+	1	+	+	1	1	1	.	
G rhiz	<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> O. Targ.Tozz	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	1	.	+	.	.	9	IV
G rhiz	<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	+	+	.	.	1	+	+	+	1	.	+	+	9	IV
P scap	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.	.	2	1	1	1	2	2	6	III
G rad	<i>Dioscorea communis</i> L. Caddick & Wilkin	1	.	.	+	+	+	2	1	6	III
G rhiz	<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	.	.	1	1	2	.	1	.	.	1	.	.	5	III
G bulb	<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	+	.	+	.	1	.	1	4	II
P caesp	<i>Arbutus unedo</i> L.	.	.	.	2	.	2	.	+	3	II
NP	<i>Rosa sempervirens</i> L.	+	+	2	I
P lian	<i>Rubia peregrina</i> L.	3	.	+	2	I
H caesp	<i>Ampelodesmos mauritanicus</i> (Poir.) T.Durand & Schinz	.	.	.	+	1	1
G rhiz	<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> L.	.	.	.	+	1	I
Other species															
H scap	<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.	1	+	.	+	1	.	1	1	2	3	1	1	10	IV
T scap	<i>Urtica urens</i> L.	1	+	+	1	.	.	+	+	6	III
G rhiz	<i>Arum italicum</i> Mill.	1	1	.	.	2	.	.	1	4	II
T scap	<i>Mercurialis annua</i> L.	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	.	3	II
G bulb	<i>Oxalis pes-caprae</i> L.	1	2	I
P scap	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L.	2	1	I

Diagnostic species. *Phillyrea latifolia* (dom.), *Viburnum tinus*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Clematis cirrhosa*; *Asparagus asparagoides* (anthropogenic variant).

Short description. Dense maquis forest of evergreen sclerophyllous scrub, (4)5–6(7) m high, with closed or almost closed canopy structure, clearly dominated by *Phillyrea latifolia*, which is constantly associated with *Arbutus unedo* and *Viburnum tinus*. *Pistacia lentiscus* also frequently appears, as well as various lianas such as *Clematis cirrhosa*, *Asparagus acutifolius*, *Smilax aspera*, *Rubia peregrina* and *Dioscorea communis*. Compared with the *Pistacio*

lentisci-Quercetum ilicis subass. *viburnetosum tini*, in this community the presence of *Quercus ilex* is more sporadic and with composed of shrub specimens. The herbaceous component is quite poor and scattered – particularly in the most intact aspects – made up of bulbous and rhizomatous species (*Arisarum vulgare*, *Acanthus mollis*, *Arum italicum*, *Allium subhirsutum*), as well as hosting a significant presence of woody plant seedlings (Fig. 7a–c).

Substrate/parent material and soil. The community is linked to sandy soils on Quaternary calcarenites, in contexts that are more xeric and draining than those colonized

Figure 7. (a) Maquis forest of the *Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova on the calcarenitic substrates of the Favorita Park; (b) monumental specimens of *Phillyrea latifolia* in the oldest aspects of the maquis; (c) the high naturalness is clearly evident in the undergrowth of *Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova; (d), (e) another aspect of the *Phillyrea latifolia* maquis in the *Asparagus asparagoides* variant; (f) vegetation of the *Ruto chalepensis-Oleetum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastri*, typical community of the detrital cones of Mt. Pellegrino.

by the holm oak grove of *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini*. These soils are classified as (2) Eutric Arenosol (Chromic) (IUSS WG WRB 2022).

Bioclimate. Mediterranean pluvisessional oceanic thermomediterranean thermotype and dry-subhumid ombrotype.

Syntaxonomic notes. *Phillyrea latifolia* is distributed in North-Mediterranean and Balkan countries, from southern Portugal to Bulgaria, Greece, and the Aegean islands; it also grows in North Africa (Libya to Morocco) and the Near East, from Anatolia to Syria, Lebanon, Israel, and Jordan (Browicz 1984). In Italy, this species is widespread in almost all regions, but more commonly in the centre-south of the peninsula and islands. It grows more frequently as a sporadic species, rarely playing a dominant role; it participates in aspects of Mediterranean scrub and thermophilous shrublands, but also in the establishment of oak groves and evergreen woods (Brullo et al. 2009). In the central plateau of Morocco (Barbero et al. 1981) for example, is part of thermophilous wild olive forests pertaining to the association *Phillyreo latifoliae-Oleatum sylvestris* Quézel, Barbero, Benabid, Loisel et Rivas-Martínez ex Gianguzzi et Bazan 2020 (Barbero and Quézel 1976; Barbero et al. 1981; Quézel et al. 1988; Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020b), while in Algeria it is found in formations with *Quercus canariensis* (Aimé et al. 1986). In the Iberian Peninsula, it takes part in oak forests of various types (*Quercus ilex*, *Q. coccifera*, *Q. faginea* and *Q. broteroi*) and other mesophilous formations (Costa Tenorio et al. 1997), but also in aspects of Mediterranean scrub.

For example, the *Phillyreo latifoliae-Arbutetum unedonis* (Velasco 1983) Loidi, Herrera, Olano et Silván 1994 association is described along the northern Cantabrian coast, differentiated with the subass. *typicum* and *viburnetosum tini* (Loidi et al. 1994); the first is widespread towards the sea, the second further inland. Another scrub community is also indicated for the Costa Smeralda, in the north-east of France, pertaining to *Hedero helicis-Phillyreotum latifoliae* (Géhu 2007).

On the island of Menorca (Balearic Islands) the species is present with the endemic variety *rodriguezii* (P. Monts.) O. Bolòs et Vigo, which dominates a shrubby community described as *Aro picti-Phillyreotum rodriguezii* (Bolòs et al. 1970). *Phillyrea latifolia* is also widespread in Sardinia, where it is also present in mesophilous woods with *Taxus baccata* (Bacchetta et al. 2009; Farris et al. 2012), as well as in Corsica, where it marks aspects of scrub related to *Erico arboreae-Arbutetum unedonis* subass. *phillyreotum latifoliae* (Allier and Lacoste 1980). In Italy, it is indicated as an element of the scrub but also of the undergrowth of formations mixed with *Quercus ilex* and *Q. suber*, as in the southern part of Lazio (Blasi et al. 1997); is also present in the *Carpinus orientalis* Mill. community of the *Lonicero etruscae-Carpinetum orientalis phillyreotum latifoliae* (Blasi et al. 2001). In the Apulian region, it is present in the *Phillyreo latifoliae-Calicotometum infestae* (Di Pietro and Misano 2010), in very intricate shrublands dominated by *Calicotome infesta*, widespread in the Gravina

of Laterza area. *Phillyrea latifolia* è also widespread in the eastern part of the Mediterranean region, associated with *Quercus coccifera*, as in the Balkan area (Horvat et al. 1974; Trinajstić 1995) and also in Greece (here described as *Quercococciferae-Phillyreotum mediae*; Barbero and Quézel 1976). Other communities characterized by the species are also reported in Turkey, such as *Phillyreo latifoliae-Pinetum brutiae* (Ozyigit et al. 2015) and *Pistacio-Phillyreotum latifoliae* (Özen and Kılınç 1995); the latter is probably a geovicariant association.

The *Phillyrea latifolia* maquis located on the calcarenitic substrates of the Palermo Plain is described as *Viburno tini-Phillyreotum latifoliae* Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco (Table 5, rel. 1–4; Fig. 7a–c), differentiated also an anthropogenic variant with *Asparagus asparagoides* (Table 5, rel. 5–12; Fig. 7d, e). It is a climbing species of South African origin, naturalized as far back as historic record in this area (Tropea 1907) and in other locations in Sicily (Giardina et al. 2007). It constitutes a recovery maquis, that is open and more nitrophilous, linked to areas exposed to humid northern winds coming from the Gulf of Mondello.

The synoptic table reported in Appendix 1: Table A2 compares the floristic composition of the two associations dominated by *Phillyrea latifolia* that are presented in this paper [the one (*Viburno tini-Phillyreotum latifoliae* ass. nova) and the *Teucro flavi-Phillyreotum latifoliae* ass. nova (which will be discussed later)] with the other scrub formations of the *Oleo-Ceratonion* alliance previously observed for Sicily. These are the first associations dominated by *Phillyrea latifolia* that are described in the regional territory. It can be noted that among all the Sicilian associations, the *Viburno tini-Phillyreotum latifoliae* ass. nova records a floristic composition with the lowest average number of species (equal to 12.6 per relevé); this data is also to be related with the old-growth nuclei forest present in this site and the notable environmental integrity of the community.

Vegetation series. The forest formation constitutes the best structured aspect of the “Edapho-xerophilous series north-western Sicilian, dry thermomediterranean, calcarenitic of *Phillyrea latifolia* (with *Viburnum tinus* and *Arbutus unedo*)”: *Viburno tini-Phillyreo latifoliae* sigmetum. This environmental landscape unit follows the series of *Pistacio lentisci-Quercococciferae-viburnetosum tini* sigmetum, occupying the more xeric and external sandy soils of the Palermo Plain, placed closer to the colluvial substrates. Along the slopes of Mt. Pellegrino, it in turn leaves room for the series of wild olive trees (*Ruto chalepensis-Oleo sylvestri cercidetosum siliquastris* sigmetum).

Synchorology. The *Viburno tini-Phillyreotum latifoliae* ass. nova constitutes a community of relict maquis, potentially linked to the coastal calcarenites of the western sector of Sicily; however, it is only known in these small areas of the Palermo Plain, having been almost destroyed by man for the benefit of cultivation and urban development.

Eunis code. F5.51A (*Phillyrea* thickets). *Natura 2000 code* – 5330 (Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-desert scrub).

Number of nuclei and total coverage (in ha). 9 nuclei (for 9,32 ha of coverage).

***Ruto chalepensis-Oleatum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastrum* Gianguzzi et Bazan 2020**

Holotypus. Rel. 15, table S1 in Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a.

Phytosociological data. Table 6.

Syntaxonomic notes. Scientific contributions to the phytosociological characterization of communities of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* have recently been produced for Sicily (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a) and the Mediterranean Region (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020b), where these forest formations show notable climatic potential in the more xeric bioclimatic belts. In Sicily, they are often represented with small nuclei and a fragmentary distribution (Gi-

Table 6. *Ruto chalepensis-Oleatum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastrum* [Column 1: synoptic table (from Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a, table S1, rels. 13–16); Col. 2: rel. 1, near Bosco Vecchio (1.6.2023, L. Gianguzzi and O. Caldarella)].

	Column (n°)	1	2
Life form	Relevé number	-	1
	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	-	150
	Slope (%)	-	30
	Aspect	-	W
	Area (m ²)	-	100
	Total cover (%)	-	90
	Tree cover (%)	-	100
	Herb cover (%)	-	40
	Average tree height (m)	-	3,2
	No. of species per relevé	-	21
Char. and diff. of association and subass. <i>oleetosum sylvestris</i>			
P caesp	<i>Olea europaea</i> L. var. <i>sylvestris</i> (Mill.) Lehr	4	5
P caesp	<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i> L.	4	3
Ch suffr	<i>Ruta chalepensis</i> L.	4	+
P caesp	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	3	2
Diff. subass. <i>cercidetosum siliquastrum</i>			
P scap	<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> L.	4	2
H caesp	<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forsk.) Chiov.	4	1
Char. of alliance and order			
Ch frut	<i>Teucrium flavum</i> L.	4	2
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	4	1
Ch frut	<i>Stachys major</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	4	+
Ch frut	<i>Asparagus albus</i> L.	3	1
G bulb	<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	4	+
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	2	3
P caesp	<i>Anagyris foetida</i> L.	2	.
P caesp	<i>Ceratomia siliqua</i> L.	1	.
Char. of class			
G rhiz	<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	4	1
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.	4	1
G rhiz	<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	3	+
G rhiz	<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> O.Targ.Tozz.	4	+
P caesp	<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	3	+
P lian	<i>Rubia peregrina</i> L.	3	.
P succ	<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> (L.) Mill.	.	1
Other species			
H scap	<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.	4	1
G bulb	<i>Oxalis pes-caprae</i> L.	4	1
H scap	<i>Ferula communis</i> L.	2	+
H caesp	<i>Oloptum miliaceum</i> (L.) Röser & H.R.Hamasha	2	.
G rhiz	<i>Asphodelus ramosus</i> L.	2	.
H caesp	<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> (L.) Stapf subsp. <i>hirta</i>	2	.
H scap	<i>Bituminaria bituminosa</i> (L.) E.H.Stirt.	2	.
Ch suffr	<i>Centranthus ruber</i> (L.) DC. subsp. <i>ruber</i>	1	.
H scap	<i>Thapsia garganica</i> L. subsp. <i>garganica</i>	1	.

anguzzi et al. 2020; Bazan et al. 2021; Guarino et al. 2021; Riveccio et al. 2020, 2021; Tavilla et al. 2021), as a result of deforestation and anthropic transformations. The *Ruto chalepensis-Oleatum sylvestris* association is described for the regional area of Sicily (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a), limited to basiphilous substrates (limestones, marl, calcarenites, etc.) and differentiated into various sub-associations. The subassociation *cercidetosum siliquastrum* has been indicated for the xeric detrital slopes of the carbonate reliefs (limestone and dolomite) of north-western Sicily, between Palermo and Trapani (Gianguzzi et al. 2012a).

Diagnostic species. *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* (dom.), *Euphorbia dendroides*, *Ruta chalepensis*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Cercis siliquastrum*, *Cenchrus setaceus*.

Short description. Dense scrub-forest, clearly dominated by *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris*, (3–)5–6 m high (potentially even over 12–15 m), linked to detrital-clastic slopes and with a variable bi- or tri-stratified structure. Various thermophilous species of the order *Pistacio-Rhamnetalia alaterni* are associated with it and of the *Oleo-Ceratonion siliquae* alliance, such as *Euphorbia dendroides*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Ruta chalepensis*, *Cercis siliquastrum* [tree native to south-eastern Europe and Asia Minor, common in central Italy but rarer in Sicily (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a)] and *Cenchrus setaceus* [invasive and sub-cosmopolitan species of subtropical origin, now widely naturalized on the island, where it shows a highly competitive pioneer character compared to other thermophilous perennial grasses (Gianguzzi et al. 1996; Pasta et al. 2010). The community is found along the western slope of Mt. Pellegrino, at altitudes between approximately 80–100 and 300–350 m a.s.l., in markedly xeric and sunny localities, with exposure to the south and southwest (Fig. 7f).

Substrate/parent material and soil. Forest formation is linked to detrital cones and detrital-clastic materials in sunny and xeric sites, along the slopes of Mt. Pellegrino. These soils are classified as Skeletic Regosol (Ochric) (IUSS WG WRB 2022).

Bioclimate. Mediterranean pluviseasonal oceanic thermomediterranean thermotype, dry-subhumid ombrotype (Gianguzzi et al. 1996, 2015, 2016b; Gianguzzi and La Mantia 2000).

Vegetation series. The forest formation constitutes the best structured aspect of the “Edapho-xerophilous and heliophilous series north-western Sicilian, dry thermomediterranean, colluvial (calcareous-dolomitic) of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* (with *Euphorbia dendroides* and *Cercis siliquastrum*)”: *Ruto chalepensis-Oleo sylvestris cercidetosum siliquastrum* sigmetum. The secondary aspects mainly consist of shrub vegetation of *Euphorbia dendroides* [*Rhamno alaterni-Euphorbietum dendroidis* Géhu et Biondi 1997 subass. *euphorbietosum bivonae* (Gianguzzi, Ilardi et Raimondo 1996) Gianguzzi, Cuttonaro, Cusimano et Romano 1996], grassland vegetation with *Cenchrus setaceus* (*Penniseto setacei-Hyparrhenietum hirtae* Gianguzzi, Ilardi et Raimondo 1996) and therophytic meadows of the class *Trachynietea distachiae* (e.g. *Thero-Sedetum caerulei* Brullo 1975). In fact, compared with the other forest for-

mations represented in the survey area, the *Ruto chalepensis-Oleetum sylvestris* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastris* are generally more isolated and less extensive. This is because these xeric slopes are mainly reforested with conifers, apart from small plots that have been historically used for dry crops (olive groves, carob groves, almond groves, prickly pear groves, etc.). Crop abandonment and recent fires have partly favoured the *Cenchrus setaceus* prairie (*Penniseto setacei-Hyparrenietum hirtae*), in addition to the evolution of the serial mosaic mentioned previously.

Near the rocky walls, the series comes into catenal contact with the *microgeosigmatum* of the cliffs, dominated by the chasmophytic vegetation of the *Scabioso creticae-Centauretum ucraiae* Brullo et Marcenò 1979, partly altered by the invasiveness of *Opuntia ficus-indica*. In the shaded part of the debris slopes, in the north/north-west exposures, the sigmetum is replaced by the ombrophilous

series of *Phillyrea latifolia*, belonging to the scrub of *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreantum latifoliae* ass. nova, described in the following paragraph.

Synchorology. North-western Sicily: Mt. Pellegrino (Palermo) and Mt. Sparacio (Trapani) (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2020a).

Eunis code. G2.41 (Wild *Olea europaea* woodland). *Natura 2000 code* – 9320 (*Olea* and *Ceratonion* forests).

Number of nuclei and total coverage (in ha). 6 nuclei (for 1,52 ha of coverage).

***Teucrio flavi-Phillyreantum latifoliae* Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco**

Holotypus. Rel. 9, Table 7.

Phytosociological data. Table 7, Appendix 1: Table A2 (column 24).

Table 7. *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreantum latifoliae* Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova: rel. 1, Vallone del Porco (28.12.2016, L. Gianguzzi); rels. 2–5, above the racecourse (10.11.2012, L. Gianguzzi); rel. 6, near Roccia dello Schiavo (8.5.2015, L. Gianguzzi); rels. 7–10, near Roccia dello Schiavo (1.6.2023, L. Gianguzzi). Asterisk indicates the type relevé.

	Relevé number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9*	10		
	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	150	100	110	120	200	90	100	120	150	150		
	Slope (%)	40	55	50	50	50	15	35	35	35	30		
	Aspect	NW	NW	NW	NW	NW	NW	W	NW	NW	W		
Life form	Area (m ²)	150	200	150	150	150	100	100	100	100	100	Presence	Frequency
	Total cover (%)	100	95	100	100	100	100	95	100	100	100		
	Tree cover (%)	100	80	80	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
	Herb cover (%)	20	80	80	20	20	20	10	10	10	10		
	Average tree height (m)	3.5	3.8	4.0	4.0	4.0	3.2	3.2	4.0	4.0	5.5		
	No. of species per relevé	15	15	14	17	18	13	16	14	13	14		
Char. and diff. of assoc.													
P caesp	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	10	V
P caesp	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	10	V
Ch frut	<i>Teucrium flavum</i> L.	3	1	2	2	+	+	1	2	3	+	10	V
P caesp	<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i> L.	2	1	2	1	1	.	+	1	+	1	9	V
P caesp	<i>Olea europaea</i> L. var. <i>syvestris</i> (Mill.) Lehr	1	2	1	1	.	2	1	.	1	2	8	IV
Char. all. Oleo-Ceratonion and ord. Pistacio-Rhamnetalia alaterni													
P caesp	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	+	1	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	4	10	V
P lian	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	.	2	+	+	+	2	1	1	1	2	9	V
Ch suffr	<i>Stachys major</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	.	.	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	6	III
P caesp	<i>Ceratonia siliqua</i> L.	.	2	1	1	.	.	1	.	.	1	5	III
Ch frut	<i>Asparagus albus</i> L.	1	.	.	.	+	2	I
P caesp	<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	3	1	I
Char. cl. Quercetea ilicis													
G rhiz	<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	2	1	1	.	1	1	2	2	1	2	9	V
G rhiz	<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> O.Targ.Tozz.	1	2	2	2	2	+	+	+	.	.	8	IV
P lian	<i>Rubia peregrina</i> L.	1	+	.	+	+	2	+	.	+	.	7	IV
G rhiz	<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	+	.	.	+	+	1	.	1	.	2	6	III
P scap	<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	.	2	.	1	1	.	2	.	.	.	4	II
G bulb	<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	1	+	+	.	.	.	3	II
Ch suffr	<i>Ruta chalepensis</i> L.	1	.	.	.	+	2	I
G rad	<i>Dioscorea communis</i> (L.) Caddick & Wilkin	+	1	I
NP	<i>Rosa sempervirens</i> L.	+	1	I
Other species													
H scap	<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.	5	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	1	1	10	V
G bulb	<i>Biarum tenuifolium</i> (L.) Schott	.	.	+	+	+	.	+	1	.	.	5	III
G bulb	<i>Oxalis pes-caprae</i> L.	2	1	2	+	4	II
T scap	<i>Mercurialis annua</i> L.	.	1	+	+	.	+	4	II
G bulb	<i>Umbilicus horizontalis</i> (Guss.) DC.	+	+	+	3	II
H caesp	<i>Oloptum miliaceum</i> (L.) Röser & H.R.Hamasha	+	1	I
H ros	<i>Asplenium ceterach</i> L.	+	.	.	1	I
G bulb	<i>Squilla maritima</i> (L.) Steinh.	+	.	1	I

Diagnostic species. *Phillyrea latifolia* (dom.), *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Teucrium flavum*, *Euphorbia dendroides* and *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris*.

Short description. Dense, intricate, and impenetrable scrub, clearly dominated by *Phillyrea latifolia*, 3–5 (6) m high, frequently associated with *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Euphorbia dendroides*, and *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris*, precisely indicated as diagnostic of the characteristic combination of the community, together with *Teucrium flavum*, a lithophilous-glareicola fruticose species, also common in the undergrowth (Fig. 8a–c). Compared with the other association with *Phillyrea latifolia* previously described for calcarenites of the Palermo Plain (*Viburno tini-Phillyreantum latifoliae* ass. nova), *Viburnum tinus* and *Arbutus unedo* are also absent. The herbaceous layer is mainly composed of rhizomatous and bulbous plants, such as *Acanthus mollis*, *Arisarum vulgare* and *Allium subhirsutum*.

Substrate/parent material and soil. The community is linked to detrital-clastic materials along the slopes of Mt. Pellegrino; however, it prefers shady, ventilated, and fresh sites exposed to the north/north-west, subjected to humid currents coming from the Gulf of Mondello. The parent materials belong to the Quaternary complex of Western Sicily, a calcarenitic-sandy-silty complex (Palermo Calcarenites) with mainly lithoid clasts, composed of calcite and siliceous rocks fragments and monocrystalline quartz (sparitic grains and small amounts of bioclasts). These soils are classified as Skeletic Regosol (Ochric) (IUSS WG WRB 2022).

Bioclimate. Mediterranean pluvisesonal oceanic (thermomediterranean thermotype and dry-subhumid ombrotype).

Vegetation series. The forest formation constitutes the best structured aspect of the “Edapho-xerophilous and ombrophilous series north-western Sicilian, thermomediterranean from dry to subhumid, colluvial (calcareous-dolomitic) of *Phillyrea latifolia* (with *Pistacia terebinthus* and *Teucrium flavum*)”: *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreo latifoliae* sigmetum). In the sunniest xeric parts of the slopes of Mt. Pellegrino landscape unit, it is replaced by the wild olive series (*Ruto chalepensis-Oleo sylvestris* sub-ass. *cercidetosum siliquastris* sigmetum), while upwards it connects the microgeotype of the cliffs, mainly characterized by the chasmophytic vegetation of the *Scabioso creticae-Centauretum ucraiae* association.

Synchorology. Known for Mt. Pellegrino, but probably also present in other locations in the Palermo Mts.

Eunis code. F5.51A (*Phillyrea* thickets).

Natura 2000 code. 5330 (Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-desert scrub).

Number of nuclei and total coverage (in ha). 2 nuclei (for 3,20 ha of coverage).

Old or “monumental” trees and shrubs

Old trees are declining in forests around the world (Lindenmayer et al. 2012) because of the consumption of

natural resources which, also threatens their survival (Rigoni Stern 1990). They significantly impact the biodiversity of an area and are gaining increasing attention as indicators of sustainable forest management (e.g. Forest Europe 2015). In fact, once silvicultural maturity has been reached, centenarian trees contribute to increasing the ecological value of ecosystems, because of an increase in biomass (variable depending on the age, size, and environmental conditions of the sites), and the development of a diversified range of microhabitats. This is reflected in the species of flora and fauna (at various levels), with an important contribution also made to the conservation of saproxylic species (Siitonen and Ranius 2015).

Our first census of these old or “monumental” trees growing in the study area was carried out on 48 specimen concentrated on a relatively small surface (Fig. 2), whose data are summarized in Appendix 1: Table A3.

Among these surveyed old specimens, the following deserve particular mention: a) the “monumental” *Olea europaea* var. *europaea* specimen, with a maximum trunk circumference of 11.10 m (at the stump) and 8.18 m (at breast height) (Fig. 8e); whose estimated age is about 1,000 years-old (Schicchi and Raimondo 2007); b) some *Quercus ilex* specimens that are 12–15 m tall, with a maximum circumference varying between 4.5 and 5.3 m (at the stump) and of 2–3 m (at the breast height); c) some *Phillyrea latifolia* specimen, that are over 15 m tall, with maximum circumference of about 3 m (at the stump) and 1 m (at breast height) with these measurements being quite unusual for this species); d) the *Pistacia terebinthus* specimen that is about 13 m tall, with a maximum circumference over 3 m (at the stump) and about 1 m (main branch at the breast height); e) some *Arbutus unedo* specimen that are between 6.5 and 8 m tall, with a maximum circumference between 1.95 and 2.95 m (at the stump) and up to 0.72 m (main branch at breast height); f) an over 200 year-old specimen of *Pistacia lentiscus*, with a maximum circumference of 2.25 m (at the stump).

Rare vascular plants

In addition to some rare species of vascular flora, there are also other species of bryophytes, lichens, and mushrooms, in Sicily that have also exclusively been recognized in this area and/or in just a few other locations, further demonstrating the important conservation role of the site and the forest formations investigated.

Viburnum tinus

Small thermophilic shrub, forming part – together with other species, such as *Coriaria myrtifolia* L., *Arbutus unedo*, and *Phillyrea latifolia* – of what is known as the “paleo-Mediterranean” element, typical of past eras with a subtropical climate (Ladero Álvarez 1976; Domínguez and Martínez 1993). It has a fragmentary and relict distribution throughout the indigenous area (Pignatti

Figure 8. (a) *Teucrium flavum*, typical element of cliffs and stony slopes, characteristic of the *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova; (b), (c) aspects of the *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova, ombrophilous community along the detrital slopes of Mt. Pellegrino; (d) *Cryphaea heteromalla* very rare species in Sicily, found in the Bosco Niscemi, on the trunks of *Quercus ilex*; (e) multi-centennial specimen of *Olea europaea* var. *europaea* in the Favorita Park; (f) *Fuscoporia torulosa* (Pers.) T.Wagner & M.Fisch. wood rot species on *Arbutus unedo* stump.

1982; Karlson et al. 2005) and is also quite rare in Sicily. In addition to this area (Brullo and Marcenò 1985; Gianguzzi et al. 1996), it is also reported in the following other locations: a) above the Rotoli Cemetery, near Palermo (Gianguzzi et al. 1996); b) Sicani Mts. [Sibilla coast (Bazan et al. 2007), Santa Maria del Bosco, Cozzo Danesi, Bosco di Santo Adriano, northern slope of Mt. Gristia (Gianguzzi et al. 2016a)]; c) Madonie Mts. (Gianguzzi and Bazan 2017) in Gibilmanna; d) Mt. San Giuliano (Pasta and La Mantia 2021); e) Mt. Conca (Pasta and La Mantia 2021); f) Mt. Etna (Brullo et al. 2009).

Arbutus unedo

Species with a circum-Mediterranean distribution that extends as far as the Atlantic, where it reaches Ireland; it is also present in the Canary Islands. In Sicily, it grows between 50 and 1,050 m a.s.l., with optimum levels between 300–400 and 700–900 m a.s.l. (Sparacio et al. 2022), preferring siliceous or decarbonated substrates. It is sometimes also found as an element of the garrigue (Gianguzzi et al. 2016b), although it is more frequent in maquis scrubland (Costanzo et al. 1998; Gianguzzi 1999; Brullo et al. 2003), evergreen oak forests (*Quercus suber* and *Q. ilex*; Brullo et al. 2009), or even pine forests of *Pinus pinea* (Brullo et al. 2003), *P. halepensis* (Brullo et al. 2009), and *P. pinaster* subsp. *escarena* (Gianguzzi 1999). *Arbutus unedo* is quite widespread along the Tyrrhenian slopes of the Peloritani (on metamorphites), the Nebrodi (on sandstones, between Caronia and Tusa) and the Madonie Mts. (between Castelbuono, Pollina, Cefalù and Gratteri, also on sandstones), including the volcanic islands of the Aeolian Archipelago (apart from Vulcano and Stromboli). However, in the western sector of Sicily, it becomes very rare, and is generally associated with relict localities: a) Bosco Niscemi, in the Palermo Plain (on calcarenites; Figs 6c, 8f); b) coastal limestone-dolomite reliefs battered by humid marine winds (in sites exposed to the north and sheltered from fires), such as Mt. Gallo (M. S. Margherita; unpublished data), Mt. Cofano (Gianguzzi and La Mantia 2008), and Marettimo Island (Mt. Campana; Brullo et al. 2009; Gianguzzi et al. 2006, 2023); c) arenaceous outcrops, such as near Cozzo Secco (Borgetto, province of Palermo; Gianguzzi et al. 2008), Bosco Gaggera (Calatafimi, province of Trapani; Gianguzzi and Bazan, in Riviuccio et al. 2022), and Bosco Scorace (Buseto Palizzolo, province of Trapani; Scuderi et al. 1994). It reappears, always sporadically, in the plains of south-western Sicily between Marsala and Sciacca, on the internal hills of Agrigento, Caltanissetta, and Enna, and is more common in isolated areas of the Sicani Mts. and the Iblean sector (Sparacio et al. 2022).

Other rare vascular plants

Among the other rarities that stand out in the floristic entourage of the communities, the following should also be mentioned: a) *Cistus salviifolius*, a typical species of acidophilic/calcifugal submontane hilly garrigues (Gianguzzi et

al. 2015), which is currently very rare in the Palermo Plain (only a few sporadic individuals have been detected); b) *Limodorum abortivum*, an uncommon and localized entity, that had already been identified in the territory, but could no longer be confirmed in recent times (Künkele and Lorenz 1995; Raimondo et al. 1996); c) *Acis autumnalis*, also typical of garrigues, uncommon (La Rosa et al. 2021).

Bryophytes

Bryophytes also play an important role within old-growth forests (Campisi et al. 2020). Investigations carried out in the Bosco Niscemi have led to the discovery of species that are typical of Mediterranean woods, some of which are quite rare. This is the case of *Cryphaea heteromalla* (Hedw.) D.Mohr – which has been identified in Sicily so far in very few other residual localities – in addition to *Hypnum cupressiforme* Hedw. and *Leptodon smithii* (Hedw.) Weber & D.Mohr, which have also never previously been found at such low altitudes and in contexts so close to the urban environment.

Cryphaea heteromalla (Hedw.) D.Mohr

This is a suboceanic-Mediterranean epiphytic species of the *Cryphaeaceae* Schimp., sensitive to air pollution (Dierßen 2001), and indicated in regression for some European areas (Sérgio et al. 1994). In Sicily, it is quite rare; so far it has only been recognized in only three other localities, all of which are at high altitudes. Two of them are located on isolated reliefs in the north-western sector, specifically Mt. Bonifato (Alcamo) and Mt. San Giuliano (Erice), both on artificially planted conifer populations; the third concerns the island of Pantelleria (Raimondo and Dia 1980; Raimondo et al. 1981), on natural woodland formations (Lo Giudice 1991; Gianguzzi 1999). A small population had also been reported for the Palermo Mts. (Dia et al. 2000), however this can no longer be confirmed, following recent devastating fires. Therefore, its discovery in the Bosco Niscemi, on the trunks of *Phillyrea latifolia*, constitutes an interesting confirmation of this species for northern Sicily (Fig. 8d).

Lichens

References on the lichenological component relating to the investigation area are lacking, apart from a study by Giovenco et al. (1996) on epiphytic lichens as biomonitors of air pollution in the urban area of Palermo. Our recent sampling within the forest nuclei of the Bosco Niscemi also confirmed the important role of the cryptogamic component. Some of the lichens present with greater frequency and coverage values include *Parmotrema perlatum* (Huds.) M. Choisy, *Punctelia subrudecta* (Nyl.) Krog., and *Ramalina canariensis* J. Steiner., which are generally quite common in the Mediterranean area. The presence of species of conservation interest was also detected (according

to Nimis 2024), including *Bacidia rosella* (Pers.) De Not., as well as the epiphytic *Gyalecta derivata* (Nyl.) H.Olivier, *Ramalina roesleri* (Schaer.) Nil. and *Waynea stoechadiana* (Abbassi Maaf & Cl.Roux) Cl.Roux & P.Clerc.

***Bacidia rosella* (Pers.) De Not.**

It is a nemoral species, rare globally, with wide distribution in Europe and northern Africa, in areas with a mild temperate to Mediterranean-Atlantic climate. It is indicated as rapidly declining in most of its distribution area, and indeed reported in “Red Lists” for many countries, such as Austria, Denmark, Germany, Norway, Sweden, and Switzerland. In Italy, it has been found in open and humid woods, even in riparian ecosystems, localized on deciduous trees (especially of the *Acer* and *Fraxinus* genera), but also evergreens, such as *Quercus ilex*. It is listed as “possibly extinct” in much of northern Italy as well as “locally abundant” in suitable habitats in southern Italy. It is included in the “Red List of Italian epiphytic lichens” as “Near threatened” (Nascimbene et al. 2013).

***Gyalecta derivata* (Nyl.) H. Olivier**

This species is widespread in Europe and northern Africa. In Italy, it is mainly widespread along the Tyrrhenian side of the Peninsula, where it is considered “very rare” (in the humid Mediterranean belt) to “extremely rare” (Nimis 2024). In Sicily, has only been identified on Marettimo Island (Nimis et al. 1994); therefore, the analysed locality represents the first report for the regional area. Similar to the previous species, it is also included in the “Red List of Italian epiphytic lichens” as “Near threatened” (Nascimbene et al. 2013).

Fungi

Mycocenological studies have demonstrated the significance of the relationships between old forest formations and fungi, with the latter providing the forest with the “pabulum” of organic substance (Barluzzi et al. 1991); in fact, important correlations, trophic and otherwise, can be hypothesized between the woody component of the same communities (trees, shrubs and lianas) and the saprotrophic, in particular lignicolous and leaf litter components. Macrofungus diversity in forest ecosystems is strongly influenced by different management practices (Tomao et al. 2020). Unmanaged forests are distinguished by the richness of wood-inhabiting fungi and indicator species. In contrast, ectomycorrhizal species are more diverse in managed stands, whereas terrestrial saprotrophs are highly diversified in both managed and unmanaged mixed forests (Dvořák et al. 2017). Specific investigations carried out on the mycological flora in the Bosco Niscemi (Venturella et al. 2001; Ferraro et al. 2022) led to the discovery of 295 taxa in the site (30 Ascomycetes and 265 Basidiomycetes), in addition to *Eichleriella leucophaea*, a very rare lignicolous entity has recently been found (Saitta 2015), which will be discussed below. The most representative families

are Tricholomataceae (61 taxa), Agaricaceae (24 taxa), Russulaceae (18 taxa), and Cortinariaceae (16 taxa). The numerically richest genera are *Amanita* Pers. and *Agaricus* L. (13 taxa), *Russula* Pers. (11 taxa), and *Tricholoma* (Fr.) Staude (11 taxa). The occurrence of infrequent species such as *Trichoglossum hirsutum* (Pers.) Boud. (Geoglossaceae) and *Hydnocystis piligera* Tul. & C. Tul. (Pyronemataceae) and the rare *Typhula fistulosa* (Holmsk.) Olariaga (Typhulaceae) is noteworthy. Significant ecological adaptability of species usually found in Sicily at altitudes above 800 m, such as *Rubroboletus satanas* (Lenz) Kuan Zhao & Zhu L. Yang (Boletaceae), *Hygrophorus russula* (Schaeff. ex Fr.) Kauffman (Hygrophoraceae), *Lactarius mairei* Malençon (Russulaceae), *Phellodon niger* (Fr.) P.Karst. (Thelephoraceae), *Aureoboletus gentles* (Quél.) Pouzar (Boletaceae), and *Tricholoma acerbum* (Bull. ex Pers.) Quél. (Tricholomataceae) has been detected. Another infrequent species is *Mollisia cinerea* (Batsch) P.Karst. (Mollisiaceae), confirming its lowest presence in the most disturbed clear-cut forests. Among other taxa, *Xylaria polymorpha* (Pers.) Grev. (Xylariaceae) and *Hymenoscyphus serotinus* (Pers.) W.Phillips (Helotiaceae) are old-growth forest indicators (Schmid and Helfer 1999; Parmasto 2001).

***Eichleriella leucophaea* Bres.**

This is a species with a wide distribution, albeit very rare and fragmentary, with its only known locality so far for Sicily and Italy in the study area (Saitta 2015). In Europe, it is also reported in Spain (Dueñas 1997, 2002; Hernández-Crespo 2006; Prieto-García et al. 2010), France (Bourdot and Galzin 1928), Bulgaria (Pilát 1937), Poland (Bresadola 1903), Germany (Aron et al. 2005) and Norway (Saitta 2015), collected on dead wood of various forest species such as *Q. ilex* (Dueñas 2002).

Discussion and conclusions

Overall, within the study area (that extends for approximately 180 ha) 22 natural forest nuclei have been identified, covering a total wooded area of 32.92 hectares. The study led to the identification of four different communities, two of which are described as new associations. Along the transect that runs throughout the calcarenites of the Favorita Park in Palermo and the detrital slopes of Mt. Pellegrino, these communities are well distinguishable, both in floristic and ecological terms (Fig. 4). They are as follows: i) *Quercus ilex* forest (*Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* Brullo et Marcenò 1985 subass. *viburnetosum tini* Gianguzzi et al. 1996), developed on humified soils of quaternary calcarenites [Solimovic Regosol (Arenic)]; ii) *Phillyrea latifolia* maquis forest with *Arbutus unedo* and *Viburnum tinus* (*Viburno tini-Phillyreetum latifoliae* ass. nova) tied to sandy and xeric soils on quaternary calcarenites [Eutric Arenosol (Chromic)]; iii) maquis of *Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* with *Cercis siliquastrum* (*Ruto chalepensis-Oleastroetum silvestri* subass. *cercidetosum siliquastri* Gianguzzi et Bazan 2020), present on detrital-clastic materials surrounding Mt. Pellegrino [Skeletal

Regosol (Ochric)]; iv) ombrophilous maquis of *Phillyrea latifolia* with *Teucrium flavum* and *Pistacia terebinthus* (*Teucrio flavi-Phillyreum latifoliae* ass. nova), also developed on detrital-clastic materials [Skeletal Regosol (Ochric)] but located in the upper part of the shady slopes, in contact with the cliffs of Mt. Pellegrino.

The two newly described associations of *Phillyrea latifolia* maquis (positioned in the *Oleo sylvestris-Ceratonion siliquae*, cl. *Quercetea ilicis* alliance), are of syntaxonomic interest because they represent the first plant communities dominated by this species to be described for Sicily. Both these paraclimactic forest communities are linked to the thermo-Mediterranean belt; they have a rather limited distribution, constituting interesting examples of residual stands that have been destroyed elsewhere by the anthropogenic degradation of the territory.

All these ancient forest communities display an extraordinary richness in necromass, in particular in Bosco Niscemi, where the presence of dead wood and litter forms other useful habitats where bryophytic, lichen and saprophagous species can establish themselves.

The synoptic table (Appendix 1: Table A1) comparing the *Pistacio-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini* identified in the study area (column 3) with similar communities already described for Sicily, shows that the average number of species per relevé is significantly lower here (Fig. 5); the data is evidently correlated to the integrity and maturity of plant formation. This is especially the case of the Bosco Niscemi forest (Fig. 6a–f), where the low floristic richness datum is probably related to the old age of the forest stands and to the low degree of disturbance, which effectively limited the occurrence of synanthropic or alien invasive species (these latter are quite common along the outer edge of the forest, e.g., *Oxalis pes-caprae*, *Cenchrus setaceus*, etc.). Centenarian or “monumental” plants are also frequent, including small trees (e.g. *Phillyrea latifolia*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *P. terebinthus*, etc.), whose dimensions and dendrometric parameters were also found to be unusual for Sicily in some cases (see Appendix 1: Table A3).

The results of this paper demonstrate that a large part of the forest stands occurring in the Favorita Park fall almost perfectly within the definition of “old-growth forests” as defined by the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (MASAF) Guidelines, aimed at the establishment of a national network of Italian old-growth forests (Ministerial Decree of 5 April 2023 in G.U.R.I. S.G. n. 138/2023). The forest stands identified in this study area satisfy all three of the criteria established in the aforementioned guidelines, namely: 1) the presence of coherent spontaneous native species...; 2) a characteristic biodiversity, deriving from the absence of disturbances for at least 60 years; 3) the presence of “serial stages linked to spontaneous regeneration and senescence” identifiable both in the outer fringe of the wooded stands and in the clearings inside the woods. In particular, the “absence of disorders for at least 60 years” revealed in some sectors of the study area is surprising, especially if one considers that these sectors are next to urbanized areas. In fact, the only significant disturbance suffered by the park was caused by the

construction of two important vehicle access roads connecting the city and the seaside resort of Mondello.

Indeed, some Mediterranean elements of the vascular flora present in the study area stand out because they are infrequent in western Sicily. This is, for example, the case of some woody plants, especially *Viburnum tinus* and *Arbutus unedo*, but also *Phillyrea media* (which is even present as dominant species of the forest bush, and with plants over 12–15 m tall). Other shrubs worth mentioning include *Cistus salvifolius* and *Emerus major* subsp. *emeroides*. Among herbaceous species, *Limodorum abortivum* and *Acis autumnalis* are also unusual throughout the Palermo Plain. Phytogeographically important bryophytes are also present, such as the very rare *Cryphaea heteromalla*, whose locality detected on the site is new for Sicily, *Hypnum cupressiforme* and *Leptodon smithii*, which also have never been found at such low altitudes. Lichens worth noting include *Bacidia rosella* (first record for Sicily), *Gyalecta derivata*, *Ramalina roesleri* and *Waynea stoehadiana*. The area's fungi include various saprotrophs species such as *Eichleriella leucophaea*, among others, which is the only location observed in Italy so far.

In summary, we have found a rich and varied diversity, “typical of mature forest systems”, this latter being closely related to the high degree of ecosystem renewal and senescence, the degradation of dead wood, and the integrity of food chains.

For the “minimum size of the nuclei”, the “Guidelines” of the aforementioned Ministerial Decree speak of “... an area of no less than 10 hectares. For particular cases, expressly motivated by specific characteristics... down to 2 hectares, provided that the area constitutes a single ecological-stationary, functional and structural system... The Regions may also approve provisions for the identification and protection of plant formations consistent with the characteristics of old age... but which do not reach the surfaces indicated above, designating them as islands of senescence destined to increase the structural complexity and biodiversity of forest systems...”.

The main cause of global biodiversity loss is known to be habitat destruction. This survey demonstrates that a low disturbance degree, even within an area such as Palermo affected by widespread anthropization allows a high level of precious biodiversity to be maintained.

The forest stands investigated here represent the final stage of successional dynamics, what's known as the head of different “vegetation series” inside a dynamically homogeneous area (“teselas” *sensu* Rivas-Martínez 1996). This progressive evolution of the vegetation up to the “climax” was possible because: i) after the acquisition of the area by the House of Bourbon, restrictive measures were adopted for anthropic activities; ii) after the Second World War, this area developed with total disinterest on the part of the human population, and managed to avoid urbanization and building speculation (which devastated other parts of the city) as well as being transformed by agriculture or coppicing for timber.

Consequently, the forest communities identified in this study are an example of the potential forest landscape of the coastal areas of Sicily, which has almost completely disappeared throughout the whole regional territory. The most in-

tact and interesting forest is in the “Bosco Niscemi” biotope along with the closely adjacent wooded areas, where a rather rich and peculiar biodiversity is preserved, which deserves careful protection and constant monitoring. In this regard, it would be desirable for micro-fauna diversity to also be investigated (e.g., phytophagous insects, soil microbiota, etc.).

Based on the scientific documentation produced in this paper regarding flora and vegetation, the proposal to include the investigated area among the sites of the “National Old Forest Network” recently established in Italy (Ministerial Decree of 5 april 2023) seems justified, relevant, and appropriate.

Furthermore, the Favorita site investigated here also affects the objectives referred to in the “EU Forestry Strategy for 2030 [COM (2021) 572 final]” – which has already been implemented by the Italian State – aimed at “protecting, restoring and expanding forests ... to combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss and ensure resilient and multifunctional forest ecosystems.” Indeed, the planned actions include “... the scrupulous protection of the last primary and old-growth forests in the EU...”, primarily acting on Natura 2000 sites, with the possibility of integrating them. The site is right next to the Special Conservation Area (SAC) ITA020014 (Mt. Pellegrino), which is well suited to be expanded to also protect these important old and residual forest nuclei, which were monitored and characterized with this present study.

Syntaxonomic scheme

- QUERCETEA ILICIS Br.-Bl. in Br.-Bl., Roussine et Nègre 1952
 QUERCETALIA ILICIS Br.-Bl. ex Molinier 1934 em. Rivas-Martínez 1975
 FRAXINO ORNI-QUERCION ILICIS Biondi, Casavecchia et Gigante in Biondi et al. 2013
Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis Brullo et Marcenò 1985 subass. *viburnetosum tini* Gianguzzi, Ilardi et Raimondo 1996
 PISTACIO LENTISCI-RHAMNETALIA ALATERNI Rivas-Martínez 1975
 OLEO SYLVESTRIS-CERATONION SILIQUAE Br.-Bl. ex Guinochet et Drouineau 1944
Viburno tini-Phillyreum latifoliae Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco
Ruto chalepensis-Oleetum sylvestris subass. *cercidetosum siliquastri* Gianguzzi et Bazan 2020
Teucro flavi-Phillyreum latifoliae Gianguzzi et Caldarella ass. nova hoc loco

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References

- Abate B, Catalano R, Renda P (1978) Schema geologico dei monti di Palermo (Sicilia). Bollettino della Società Geologica Italiana 97: 807–819.
- Aimé S, Bonin G, Chaabane A, Loisel R, Saoudi H (1986) Notes phytosociologiques nord-africaines: Contribution à l'étude phytosociologique des zénaies du littoral algéro-tunisien. Ecologia Mediterranea 12(3–4): 113–131. <https://doi.org/10.3406/ecmed.1986.1178>
- Allier C, Lacoste A (1980) Maquis et groupements végétaux de la série du chêne vert dans le bassin du Fango (Corse). Ecologia Mediterranea 5(1): 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.3406/ecmed.1979.954>
- Andreotta A, Ciampalini R, Moretti P, Vingiani S, Poggio G, Matteucci G, Tesconi F, Carnicelli S (2011) Forest humus forms as potential indicators of soil carbon storage in Mediterranean environments. Biology and Fertility of Soils 47(1): 31–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-010-0499-z>
- Aron A, Kahar H, Michelitsch S, Pidlich-Aigne H, Prelicz D (2005) Vorläufige Rote Liste gefährdeter Gropilze der Steiermark. Joannea Botanik 4: 45–80.
- Bacchetta G, Bagella S, Biondi E, Farris E, Filigheddu R, Mossa L (2009) Vegetazione forestale e serie di vegetazione della Sardegna (con rappresentazione cartografica alla scala 1: 350.000). Fitosociologia 46(1, suppl. 1): 3–82.
- Badalamenti E, Pasta S, La Mantia T, La Mela Veca DS (2018) Criteria to identify old-growth forests in the Mediterranean: A case study from Sicily based on literature review and some management proposals. Feddes Repertorium 129(1): 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fedr.201700009>
- Barbagallo C, Brullo S, Fagotto F (1979) Boschi di *Quercus ilex* L. del territorio di Siracusa e principali aspetti di degradazione. Pubbl. Ist. Bot. Univ. Catania, 1–24.
- Barbera G, La Mantia T, Rühl J (2009) La Conca d'Oro: trasformazione di un paesaggio agrario e riflessi sulla sostenibilità. In: Leone M, Lo Piccolo F, Schilleci F (Eds) Il paesaggio agricolo nella Conca d'Oro di Palermo. Alinea ed., Firenze, 69–95.
- Barbero M, Quézel P (1976) Les groupements forestiers de Grèce centro-méridionale. Ecologia Mediterranea 2(1): 3–86. <https://doi.org/10.3406/ecmed.1976.920>
- Barbero M, Quézel P, Rivas-Martínez S (1981) Contribution à l'étude des groupements forestiers et pré-forestiers du Maroc. Phytocoenologia 9(3): 311–412. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/9/1981/311>
- Barluzzi C, Perini C, Chiarucci A, Loppi S, De Dominicis V (1991) Relazioni fra micocenosi e fitocenosi. I. I saprotrofi lignicoli e di lettiera. Informatore Botanico Italiano 23(2–3): 163–167.
- Bartolo G, Brullo S, Marcenò C (1982) La vegetazione costiera della Sicilia sud-orientale. Contributo alla interpretazione delle fasce di vegetazione delle coste mediterranee. C.N.R., Roma, Progetto Finalizzato “Promozione della Qualità dell'Ambiente”. AQ (Balmain, N.S.W.) 1/226: 1–49.
- Bartolucci F, Peruzzi L, Galasso G, Albano A, Alessandrini A, Ardenghi NMG, Astuti G, Bacchetta G, Ballelli S, Banfi E, Barberis G, Bernardo L, Bouvet D, Bovio M, Cecchi L, Di Pietro R, Domina G, Fascetti S, Fenu G, Festi F, Foggi B, Gallo L, Gottschlich G, Gubellini L, Iamónico D, Iberite M, Jiménez-Mejías P, Lattanzi E, Marchetti D, Martinetto E, Masin RR, Medagli P, Passalacqua NG, Peccenini S, Pennesi R, Pierini B, Poldini L, Prosser F, Raimondo FM, Roma-Marzio F, Rosati L, Santangelo A, Scoppola A, Scortegagna S, Selvaggi A, Selvi F, Soldano A, Stinca A, Wagensommer RP, Wilhelm T, Conti F (2018) An updated checklist of the vascular flora native to Italy. Plant Biosystems 152(2): 179–303. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2017.1419996>

- Basilone L (2018) Lithostratigraphy of Sicily. Springer Cham, 349 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73942-7>
- Bazan G, Marino P, Schicchi R (2007) Gli habitat naturali di interesse comunitario (Direttiva 92/43/CEE) del pSIC “Monte Genuardo e Santa Maria del Bosco” (ITA020035). In: Atti 102° Congr. Soc. Bot. Ital. Palermo, 26–29 september 2007. Collana “Sicilia Foreste” 34: 283.
- Bazan G, Bacchetta G, Bagella S, Bonari G, Bonini F, Calvia G, Caria MC, Rivieccio G, Gianguzzi L (2021) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from # 21 to #25. Plant Sociology 58(1): 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2021581/09>
- Blasi C, Filesi L, Fratini S, Stanisci A (1997) Le cenosi con sughera nel paesaggio tirrenico laziale (Italia centrale). Ecologia Mediterranea 23(3–4): 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.3406/ecmed.1997.1834>
- Blasi C, Di Pietro R, Filesi L, Fortini P (2001) Syntaxonomy, chorology and dynamics of *Carpinus orientalis* communities in Central Italy. Phytocoenologia 31(1): 33–62. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/31/2001/33>
- Blasi C, Burrascano S, Maturani A, Sabatini FM (2010) Foreste vetuste in Italia. Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare, Roma, 1–24.
- Bolòs OD, Molinier R, Montserrat RP (1970) Phytosociological observations in Minorca Island. Acta Geobotanica Barcinonensis 5: 1–150.
- Bourdot H, Galzin A (1928) Hymenomycetes de France. Marcel Bry, Sceaux, 761 pp.
- Braun-Blanquet J (1964) Pflanzensoziologie, Grundzüge der Vegetationskunde. Springer Verlag, Wien-New York, 865 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-8110-2>
- Bresadola J (1903) Fungi polonici. Annales Mycologici 1: 115–117.
- Browicz K (1984) Chorology of trees and shrubs in South-West Asia and adjacent regions. Vol. 3. Polish Scientific Publishers, Warszawa Poznań, 172 pp.
- Brullo S, Marcenò C (1985) Contributo alla conoscenza della classe *Quercetea ilicis* in Sicilia. Notiziario Fitosociologico 19(1) [1984]: 183–229.
- Brullo S, Furnari F, Scelsi F (1993) Considerazioni fitosociologiche sulla vegetazione di Cava d’Ispica (Sicilia meridionale). Boll. Acc. Gioenia Sci. Nat. Catania 26(341): 49–83.
- Brullo S, Minissale P, Siracusa G, Scelsi F, Spampinato G (2003) Indagine fitosociologica sui pineti a *Pinus pinea* della Sicilia. Quaderni di Botanica ambientale e applicata 13 [2002]: 117–124.
- Brullo S, Gianguzzi L, La Mantia A, Siracusa G (2009) La classe *Quercetea ilicis* in Sicilia. Boll. Acc. Gioenia Sci. Nat. 41(369) [2008]: 1–80.
- Buffa M, Venturella G, Raimondo FM (1986) Contributi botanici alla conoscenza del verde storico a Palermo. 2. Carta della vegetazione del Parco della Favorita. Il Naturalista Siciliano 10(4, suppl.): 3–90.
- Burrascano S, Rosati L, Blasi C (2009) Plant species diversity in Mediterranean old-growth forests: A case study from central Italy. Plant Biosystems 143(1): 190–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263500802709699>
- Calvi F, Contino A, Cusimano G, Di Cara A, Frias Forcada A, Hauser S, Pellerito S (1998) Nuovi contributi alla conoscenza dell’idrogeologia della Piana di Palermo. Atti del 79° Congresso Nazionale della Società Geologica Italiana, vol. A. Palermo 21–23 september 1998, 212–215.
- Campisi P, Mannino AM, Venturella G, Ravera S (2020) A first contribution to the cryptogamic flora of “Bosco Pomieri” (Northern Sicily). Borziana 1: 35–51. <https://doi.org/10.7320/Borz.001.035>
- Capotorti G, Zavattero L, Copiz R, Del Vico E, Facioni L, Bonacquisti S, Frondoni R, Allegranza M, Attorre F, Bacchetta G, Barni E, Biondi E, Brandmayr P, Caccianiga MS, Carli E, Casavecchia S, Cerabolini BEL, Chiarucci A, Dell’Olmo L, Fascetti S, Fenu G, Galdenzi D, Gargano D, Gianguzzi LA, Manes F, Oddi L, Orsenigo S, Paolanti M, Pinna MS, Rosati L, Rossi G, Sarandrea P, Siniscalco C, Spampinato G, Tazzari ER, Tesi G, Venanzoni R, Viciani D, Blasi C (2020) Implementation of IUCN criteria for the definition of the Red List of Ecosystems in Italy. Plant Biosystems 154(6): 1007–1011. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2020.1839806>
- Casavecchia S, Allegranza, Angiolini C, Biondi E, Bonini F, Del Vico E, Fanfarillo E, Foggi B, Gigante D, Gianguzzi L, Lasen C, Maccherini S, Mariotti M, Pesaresi S, Pirone G, Poldini L, Selvi F, Venanzoni R, Viciani D, Vidali M, Ciaschetti G (2021) Proposals for improvement of Annex I of Directive 92/43/EEC: Central Italy. Plant Sociology 58(2): 99–118. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2021582/08>
- Catalano R, Abate B, Renda P (1979) Carta Geologica dei Monti di Palermo, scala 1: 50.000. Istituto di Geologia dell’Università degli Studi di Palermo.
- Catalano R, Valenti V, Albanese C, Accaino F, Sulli A, Tinivella U, Gasparo Morticelli M, Zanolla C, Giustiniani M (2013) Sicily’s fold-thrust belt and slab roll-back: The SI. RI. PRO. seismic crustal transect. Journal of the Geological Society 170(3): 451–464. <https://doi.org/10.1144/jgs2012-099>
- Costa Tenorio M, Morla Juaristi C, Sainz Ollero H (1997) Los bosques ibéricos: una interpretación geobotánica. Editorial Planeta, Barcelona, 597 pp.
- Costanzo E, Furnari F, Scelsi F, Tomaselli V (1998) Vegetazione del territorio di Bauli (Sicilia sudorientale) con cartografia 1: 10.000. Atti 6° Workshop Progetto Strategico Clima, Ambiente e Territorio nel Mezzogiorno. Taormina, 13–15 december 1995, 587–605.
- Di Pietro R, Misano G (2010) Shrubland and garrigue vegetation in the «Gravine» gorges (Apulia region, south-eastern Italy). Acta Botanica Gallica 157(2): 195–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12538078.2010.10516199>
- Di Pietro R, Conte AL, Di Marzio P, Gianguzzi L, Spampinato G, Caldarella O, Fortini P (2020) A multivariate morphometric analysis of diagnostic traits in southern Italy and Sicily pubescent oaks. Folia Geobotanica 55(3): 163–183. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12224-020-09378-0>
- Di Pietro R, Conte AL, Di Marzio P, Fortini P, Farris E, Gianguzzi L, Müller M, Rosati L, Spampinato G, Gailing O (2021) Does the genetic diversity among pubescent white oaks in southern Italy, Sicily and Sardinia islands support the current taxonomic classification? European Journal of Forest Research 140(2): 355–371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10342-020-01334-z>
- Dia MG, Campisi P, Aiello P (2000) Interessanti reperti per la brioflora siciliana. Atti 95° Congr. Soc. Bot. Ital. Messina, 28–30 september 2000, 104.
- Dierßen K (2001) Distribution, ecological amplitude and phytosociological characterization of European bryophytes. Bryophytorum Bibliotheca 56: 1–289.
- Domínguez F, Martínez F (1993) Acerca de la distribución española de *Arbutus unedo* L. (*Ericaceae*). Boletín Real Sociedad Española de Historia Natural 89(1–4): 163–179. [sección Biología]
- Dueñas M (1997) Bases corológicas de Flora Micologica Iberica. Numeros 1114–1223. Cuadernos de Trabajo de Flora Micológica Iberica 11: 1–99.
- Dueñas M (2002) Annotated list of Heterobasidiomycetous fungi for the Iberian Peninsula and Balearic Islands. Bibliotheca Mycologica 196: 1–90.
- Duro A, Piccione V, Scalia C, Zampino D (1996) Precipitazioni e temperature medie mensili in Sicilia relative al sessantennio 1926–1985. Proceedings of the 5° Workshop del Progetto Strategico CNR “Clima

- Ambiente e Territorio del Mezzogiorno". Amalfi, 28–30 April 1993, 17–103.
- Dvořák D, Vašutová M, Hofmeister J, Beran M, Hošek J, Běťák J, Burel J, Deckerová H (2017) Macrofungual diversity patterns in central European forests affirm the key importance of old-growth forests. *Fungal Ecology* 27(Part B): 145–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2016.12.003>
- Europe Forest (2015) Annex I to Madrid Ministerial Declaration: Updated Pan-European indicators for sustainable forest management, as adopted by the FOREST EUROPE Expert Level Meeting, 30 June – 2 July 2015, Madrid, Spain. In: Madrid Ministerial Declaration – 25 years together promoting Sustainable Forest Management in Europe. Forest Europe, seventh Ministerial Conference, Madrid 20–21 October 2015, 8 pp.
- Farris E, Fenu G, Bacchetta G (2012) Mediterranean *Taxus baccata* woodlands in Sardinia: A characterization of the EU priority habitat 9580. *Phytocoenologia* 41(4): 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0340-269X/2011/0041-0501>
- Ferraro V, Venturella G, Cirlincione F, Mirabile G, Gargano ML, Colasuonno P (2022) The Checklist of Sicilian Macrofungi: Second Edition. *Journal of Fungi* 8(6): 566. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8060566>
- Frascaroli F, Bhagwat S, Guarino R, Chiarucci A, Schmid B (2016) Shrines in Central Italy conserve plant diversity and large trees. *Ambio* 45(4): 468–479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-015-0738-5>
- Géhu JM (2007) Brousses autochtones, maquis néophytiques et série thermophile du Rubio-Quercetum roboris sur la Côte d’Emeraude. *Bull. Soc. Bot. Centre-Ouest NS*, 38: 37–52.
- Gianguzzi L (1999) Vegetazione e bioclimatologia dell’Isola di Pantelleria (Canale di Sicilia). *Braun-Blanquetia* 22: 3–70.
- Gianguzzi L, Bazan G (2017) Guida alle escursioni sulla vegetazione delle Alte Madonie. Workshop “Cambiamenti climatici e vegetazione di altitudine delle montagne mediterranee”. Parco delle Madonie (Sicilia), 1–4 June 2017. C.I.R.I.T.A., Università degli Studi di Palermo, 36 pp.
- Gianguzzi L, Bazan G (2020a) A phytosociological analysis of the *Olea europaea* L. var. *sylvestris* (Mill.) Lehr. forests in Sicily. *Plant Biosystems* 154(5): 705–725. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2019.1681532>
- Gianguzzi L, Bazan G (2020b) The *Olea europaea* L. var. *sylvestris* (Mill.) Lehr. forests in the Mediterranean area. *Plant Sociology* 56(2): 3–34. <https://doi.org/10.7338/pls2019562/01>
- Gianguzzi L, Bazan G (2020c) The vegetation of a historic road system in the suburban area of Monte Pellegrino (Palermo, Sicily). *Plant Sociology* 57(2): 71–103. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2020572/02>
- Gianguzzi L, La Mantia A (2000) Caratteristiche geografiche e bioclimatiche. In: Gianguzzi L, Ottonello D (Eds) *La Riserva di Monte Cofano* (Sicilia nord-occidentale). Aspetti geomorfologici, naturalistici ed etnoantropologici. Azienda Foreste Demaniali della Regione Siciliana ed., Palermo, Collana Sicilia Foreste 8, 11–24.
- Gianguzzi L, La Mantia A (2008) Contributo alla conoscenza della vegetazione e del paesaggio vegetale della Riserva Naturale Orientata “Monte Cofano” (Sicilia occidentale) (con allegata Carta sinfitosociologica della vegetazione, scala 1: 20.000). *Fitosociologia* 45(1, suppl. 1): 3–55.
- Gianguzzi L, Ilardi V, Raimondo FM (1996) La vegetazione del promontorio di Monte Pellegrino (Palermo). *Quad. Bot. ambient. appl.* 4[1993]: 79–137.
- Gianguzzi L, Scuderi L, Pasta S (2006) La flora vascolare dell’Isola di Marettimo (Arcipelago delle Egadi, Canale di Sicilia): Aggiornamento ed analisi fitogeografica. *Webbia* 61(2): 359–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00837792.2006.10670810>
- Gianguzzi L, Romano S, Caldarella O, La Rosa A (2008) Osservazioni fitosociologiche ed ecologiche su una formazione forestale a *Quercus suber* dei Monti di Palermo (Sicilia centro-occidentale) percorsa dal fuoco nell’estate del 2007. *Atti 103° Congr. Soc. Bot. Ital. Reggio Calabria*, 17–19 September 2008, 327 pp.
- Gianguzzi L, D’Amico A, Romano S (2010) Phytosociological remarks on residual woodlands of *Laurus nobilis* in Sicily. *Lazaroa* 31: 67–84. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_LAZA.2010.v31.4
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Bonventre V, Romano S, Ilardi V (2012a) Bio-ecological, phytosociological and conservation aspects of relictual and disjointed populations of *Simethis mattiazzi* (Vandelli) Sacc. (Xanthorrhoeaceae) in the Channel of Sicily. *Acta Botanica Gallica* 159(3): 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12538078.2012.737141>
- Gianguzzi L, Ilardi V, Caldarella O, Cusimano D, Cuttonaro P, Romano S (2012b) Phytosociological characterization of the *Juniperus phoenicea* L. subsp. *turbinata* (Guss.) Nym, and formations in the Italo-Tyrrhenian Province (Mediterranean Region). *Plant Sociology* 49(2): 3–28. <https://doi.org/10.7338/pls2012492/01>
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Ilardi V, Romano S (2013) Distribution, ecology, vegetation and conservation survey on the relictual population of *Carex panormitana* Guss. (Cyperaceae) in Sicily (Italy). *Webbia* 68(2): 159–175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00837792.2013.853364>
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Papini F, Romano S (2014) Vegetazione dei corsi d’acqua della Sicilia in sistemi paesaggistici con problematiche d’impatto ambientale: il bacino del Fiume Oreto (Palermo). *Atti 48° Congr. Naz. Società Italiana Scienza della Vegetazione “Scienza della Vegetazione e monitoraggio della Biodiversità”*. Roma, 17–19 September 2014, 39.
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Cuttonaro P, Gianguzzi G, Romano S (2014a) Distribution, ecology and conservation survey on the *Celtis tournefortii* subsp. *aetnensis* (Celtidaceae–Cannabaceae) populations in Sicily. *Webbia* 69(2): 325–334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00837792.2014.971586>
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Romano S (2014b) Phytosociological characterization of the *Celtis tournefortii* subsp. *aetnensis* microwoods in Sicily. *Plant Sociology* 51(2): 17–28.
- Gianguzzi L, Cusimano D, Ilardi V, Romano S (2015) Phytosociological analysis of the *Genista* sp. pl. garrigues of the *Cisto-Lavanduletea* and *Rosmarinetea officinalis* classes in the South-Tyrrhenian area (Mediterranean Region). *Plant Biosystems* 149(3): 574–588. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2014.1000425>
- Gianguzzi L, Cuttonaro P, Cusimano D, Romano S (2016a) Contribution to the phytosociological characterization of the forest vegetation of the Sicani Mountains (inland of the north-western Sicily). *Plant Sociology* 53(1): 5–42. <https://doi.org/10.7338/pls2016531/02>
- Gianguzzi L, Papini F, Cusimano D (2016b) Phytosociological survey vegetation map of Sicily (Mediterranean region). *Journal of Maps* 12(5): 845–851. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2015.1094969>
- Gianguzzi L, Castrorao Barba A, Bazan G (2017) History and forest vegetation dynamics of the Favorita Park in the Palermo suburbs (NW Sicily). In: Paradis-Grenouillet S, Aspe C, Burri S (Eds) *Abstracts of the International conference “Into the Woods. Overlapping Perspectives on the History of Ancient Forests”*. Mantova, 18–20 April 2017, 49.
- Gianguzzi L, Bagella S, Bazan G, Caria C, Cerabolini BEL, Dalla Vecchia A, Riviaccio G, Bolpagni R (2020) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from #13 to #15. *Plant Sociology* 57(1): 65–74. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2020571/07>
- Gianguzzi L, Caldarella O, Pasta S (2022) A new association of relict maquis with *Ptilostemon greuteri* (Oleo–Ceratonia, *Quercetea ilicis*), located in a circumscribed area of north-western Sicily. *Plant Sociology* 59(1): 67–83. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2022591/06>

- Gianguzzi L, Guarino R, Bazan G, Di Pietro R, Acosta ATR, Bajona E, Boliger P, Bonomi C, Camuffo A, Console C, Fascetti S, Fortini P, Frattaroli A, Mei G, Mondello F, Olivari S, Rizzieri M, Rosati L, Sarmati S, Scuderi L, Simonazzi M, Spampinato G, Viegi L, Stinca A (2023) Itineraries of the Working Group for Vegetation Science of the Italian Botanical Society – I (2022): Excursion to the Egadi Islands, Mount San Giuliano and Mount Cofano (Trapani, western Sicily, Italy). *Italian Botanist* 16: 1–57. <https://doi.org/10.3897/italianbotanist.16.103989>
- Giardina G, Raimondo FM, Spadaro V (2007) A catalogue of plants growing in Sicily. *Bocconea* 20: 5–582.
- Gigante D, Attorre F, Venanzoni R, Acosta ATR, Agrillo E, Aleffi M, Alessi N, Allegranza M, Angelini P, Angiolini C, Assini S, Azzella MM, Bagella S, Biondi E, Bolpagni R, Bonari G, Bracco F, Brullo S, Buffa G, Carli E, Caruso G, Casavecchia S, Casella L, Cerabolini BEL, Ciaschetti G, Copiz R, Cutini M, Del Vecchio S, Del Vico E, Di Martino L, Facioni L, Fanelli G, Foggi B, Frattaroli AR, Galdenzi D, Gangale C, Gasparri R, Genovesi P, Gianguzzi L, Gironi F, Giusso Del Galdo G, Gualmini M, Guarino R, Lasen C, Lastrucci L, Maneli F, Pasta S, Paura B, Perrino EV, Petraglia A, Pirone G, Poponessi S, Prisco I, Puglisi M, Ravera S, Sbrulino G, Sciandrello S, Selvaggi A, Spada F, Spampinato G, Strumia S, Tomaselli M, Tomaselli V, Uzunov D, Viciani D, Villani M, Wagensommer RP, Zitti S (2016) A methodological protocol for Annex I Habitats monitoring: The contribution of Vegetation science. *Plant Sociololy* 53(2): 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.7338/pls2016532/06>
- Giovenco A, Ottonello D, Dia G, Orecchio S (1996) Licheni ed inquinamento atmosferico nell'aria nella zona metropolitana di Palermo. *Inquinamento* 3: 48–52.
- Guarino R, Pasta S (2017) Botanical Excursions in Central and Western Sicily: Field Guide for the 60th IAVS Symposium. Palermo, 20–24 June 2017. Palermo University Press, 604 pp. <https://doi.org/10.21570/BUI-201712-1>
- Guarino R, Pasta S, Bazan G, Crisafulli A, Caldarella O, Giusso Del Galdo G, Gristina AS, Ilardi V, La Mantia A, Marcenò C, Minissale P, Sciandrello S, Scuderi L, Spampinato G, Troia A, Gianguzzi L (2021) Relevant habitats neglected by the Directive 92/43 EEC: The contribution of Vegetation Science for their reappraisal in Sicily. *Plant Sociology* 58(2): 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2021582/05>
- Guidotti S, Pignatti S, Testi A (2010) Microclimatic responses of plant communities to climatic changes: A study case in the Mediterranean coastal vegetation near Rome. *Annali di Botanica* 0: 139–148.
- GURI (2023) Ministerial Decree of 5 april 2023 – Ministry of Agriculture, of Food sovereignty and Forests. <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2023/06/15/138/sg/pdf>
- Hernández-Crespo JC (2006) SIMIL, Sistema de Información Micológica Ibérica en Línea. Real Jardín Botánico de Madrid, C.S.I.C. Proyecto Flora Micológica Ibérica I–VI (1990–2008). Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia, España. <http://rjb.csic.es/fmi/sim.php> [Last accessed on 3.10.2023]
- Hodgetts NG, Söderström L, Blockeel TL, Caspari S, Ignatov MS, Konstantinova NA, Lockhart N, Papp B, Schröck C, Sim-Sim M, Bell D, Bell NE, Blom HH, Bruggeman-Nannenga MA, Brugués M, Enroth J, Flatberg KI, Garilleti R, Hedenäs L, Holyoak DT, Hugonnot V, Kariyawasam I, Köckinger H, Kučera J, Lara F, Porley RD (2020) An annotated checklist of bryophytes of Europe, Macaronesia and Cyprus. *Journal of Bryology* 42(1): 1–116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03736687.2019.1694329>
- Horvat I, Glavač V, Ellenberg H (1974) *Vegetation Südosteuropas*. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Jena/Stuttgart, 768 pp.
- IUSS Working Group WRB (2022) World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edn. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Wien, 234 pp.
- Karlson LM, Hidayati SN, Walck JL, Milberg P (2005) Complex combination of seed dormancy and seedling development determine emergence of *Viburnum tinus* (Caprifoliaceae). *Annals of Botany* 95(2): 323–330. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mci029>
- Künkele S, Lorenz R (1995) Zum Stand der Orchideenkartierung in Sizilien. *Jahresberichte des Naturwissenschaftlichen Vereins Wuppertal* 48: 21–115.
- La Mantia T (2004) Ecologia ed agricoltura nel parco della Favorita. In: Amara O, Barbera G (Eds) *Tenuta Reale “la Favorita”: un parco tra storia e natura*. Assessorato Ambiente ed Edilizia del Comune di Palermo, 91–121.
- La Rosa A, Gianguzzi L, Salluzzo G, Scuderi L, Pasta S (2021) Last tesseræ of a fading mosaic: Floristic census and forest vegetation survey at Parche di Bilello (south-western Sicily, Italy), a site needing urgent protection measures. *Plant Sociology* 58(1): 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2020581/04>
- Ladero Álvarez M (1976) *Prunus lusitanica* L. (Rosaceae) en la Península Ibérica. *Annales Instituto Botánico Cavanilles* 33: 207–218.
- Leone M (2003) La riqualificazione delle aree verdi come elemento strategico dello sviluppo urbano sostenibile. Il caso di Palermo: simulazioni progettuali delle connessioni tra il Parco della Favorita, i tessuti urbani esistenti e il sistema paesaggistico unitario della riserva di Monte Pellegrino. *Publiciscola ed.*, Palermo, 181 pp.
- Lindenmayer DB, Laurance WF, Franklin JF (2012) Global decline in large old trees. *Science* 338(6112): 1305–1306. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1231070>
- Lo Giudice R (1991) Studio fitosociologico sulla briovegetazione epifitica della Sicilia. *Archivio Botanico Italiano* 67(1–2): 76–98.
- Loidi J, Herrera M, Olano JM, Silván F (1994) Maquis vegetation in the eastern Cantabrian coastal fringe. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 5(4): 533–540. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3235980>
- Maetke FG, Spampinato G, Londi G, Vinciguerra S (2017) Approccio alla caratterizzazione di un lembo di bosco vetusto: Il caso di Monte Egitto (Monte Etna). *L'Italia Forestale e Montana* 72(3): 169–194. <https://doi.org/10.4129/ifm.2017.3.02>
- Marcenò C, Ottonello D (1991) Osservazioni fitosociologiche su alcune leccete dei Monti di Palermo (con appendice floristica). *Atti dell'Accademia Scienze Lettere ed Arti di Palermo* (5) 11(1) [1990–91]: 121–143.
- Marchetti M, Lombardi F, Tognetti R, Chirici G (2012) Verso una rete di connessione dei boschi vetusti. *Gazzetta Ambiente* 3: 39–49.
- Mucina L, Bültmann H, Dierßen K, Theurillat J-P, Raus T, Čarni A, Šumberová K, Willner W, Dengler J, García RG, Chytrý M, Hájek M, Di Pietro R, Iakushenko D, Pallas J, Daniëls FJA, Bergmeier E, Santos Guerra A, Ermakov N, Valachovič M, Schaminée JHJ, Lysenko T, Didukh YP, Pignatti S, Rodwell JS, Capelo J, Weber HE, Solomeshch A, Dimopoulos P, Aguiar C, Hennekens SM, Tichý L (2016) Vegetation of Europe: Hierarchical floristic classification system of vascular plant, bryophyte, lichen, and algal communities. *Applied Vegetation Science* 19(S1): 3–264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12257>
- Nascimbene J, Nimis PL, Ravera S (2013) Evaluating the conservation status of epiphytic lichens of Italy: A red list. *Plant Biosystems* 147(4): 898–904. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2012.748101>
- Nimis PL (2024) ITALIC. The Information System on Italian Lichens. Version 7.0. University of Trieste, Dept. of Biology. <https://dryades.units.it/italic> [Last accessed on 9.02.2024]

- Nimis PL, Martellos S (2020) Towards a digital key to the lichens of Italy. *Symbiosis* 82(1–2): 149–155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13199-020-00714-8>
- Nimis P, Poelt J, Tretiach M, Ottonello D, Puntillo D, Vezda A (1994) Contributions to lichen floristics in Italy. VII. The Lichens of Marettimo (Egadi Islands, Sicily). *Bulletin de la Société linnéenne de Provence* 45: 247–262.
- Özen F, Kılınc M (1995) Alaçam-Gerze ve Boyabat-Durağan arasında kalan bölgenin vejetasyonu: II. Orman ve bozuk orman vejetasyonları. *Turkish Journal of Botany* 19(1): 87–105.
- Ozyigit S, Altay V, Ozyigit II, Yarci C (2015) Vegetation ecology of the Princes' Islands, Istanbul-Turkey. *Journal of Environmental Biology* 36(Special issue): 113–120.
- Parmasto E (2001) Hymenochaetoid fungi (Basidiomycota) of North America. *Mycotaxon* 79: 107–176.
- Pasta S, La Mantia T (2021) Notes on the status and the current spread of *Viburnum tinus* L. (fam. Viburnaceae) in Sicily (Italy). *Il Naturalista siciliano* (4) 45(1–4): 37–54.
- Pasta S, Badalamenti E, La Mantia T (2010) Tempi e modi di un'invasione incontrastata: *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov. in Sicilia. *Il Naturalista siciliano*, ser. 4, 34(3–4): 487–525.
- Pignatti S (1982) *Flora d'Italia*. Edagricole, Bologna I: 1–3.
- Pignatti S, Guarino R, La Rosa M (2017–2019) *Flora d'Italia*. 2nd edition. Edagricole – Business Media, Bologna – Milano, 4 vols.
- Pilát A (1937) Contribution à la connaissance des Basidiomycetes de la péninsule des Balkans. *Bulletin de la Société Mycologique de France* 53: 81–104.
- Pirajno R, Flaibani A [Eds] (2015) *Guida ai giardini pubblici di Palermo*. Fondazione Salvare Palermo onlus, 168 pp.
- Pirrone G, Buffà M, Mauro E, Sessa E (1990) *Palermo detto Paradiso di Sicilia (ville e giardini, XII–XX secolo)*. Centro Studi di Storia e Arte dei Giardini, Palermo, 285 pp.
- Ponge JF (2003) Humus forms in terrestrial ecosystems: A framework to biodiversity. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 35(7): 935–945. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(03\)00149-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(03)00149-4)
- Portal to the Flora of Italy (2023) *Portale della Flora d'Italia/Portal to the Flora of Italy*. 2023.1. <http://dryades.units.it/floritaly/> [Last accessed 12.10.2023]
- Prieto-García F, Moreno G, González A, Zamora JC (2010) *Eichleriella leucophaea*, una especie poco conocida. *Boletín de la Sociedad Micológica de Madrid* 34: 61–67.
- Quézel P, Barbero M, Benabid A, Loisel R, Rivas-Martínez S (1988) Contribution à l'étude des groupements pré-forestiers et des matorrals rifains. *Ecologia Mediterranea* 14(1): 77–122. <https://doi.org/10.3406/ecmed.1988.1208>
- Raimondo FM, Dia MG (1980) Note briogeografiche II. *Cryphaea heteromalla* (Hedw.) Mohr. In Sicilia. *Atti dell'Accademia di Scienze Lettere e Arti di Palermo* (4) 38(1): 153–171.
- Raimondo FM, Ilardi V (2009) Indagini fitosociologiche sulla vegetazione a *Bupleurum fruticosum* (Umbelliferae) del versante tirrenico della Sicilia orientale. *Il Naturalista Siciliano* (4) 33(3–4): 361–372.
- Raimondo FM, Dia MG, Villari R (1981) *Cryphaea heteromalla* (Hedw.) Mohr., nuovo reperto per la brioflora dell'Isola di Pantelleria. *Giornale Botanico Italiano* 115: 413–414.
- Raimondo FM, Gianguzzi L, Di Martino C (1996) La flora vascolare del promontorio di Monte Pellegrino (Palermo). *Quaderni di Botanica Ambientale ed Applicata* 4[1993]: 13–34.
- Rigoni Stern M (1990) *Trees: myth, pessimism and hope. The monumental trees of Italy. The Centre and North*. Abete ed., Roma, 24–27.
- Rivas-Martínez S (1996) *Geobotánica y Climatología. Discursos pronunciados en el acto de investidura de doctor «honoris causa» del exceleto señor D. Salvador Rivas-Martínez*. Universidad de Granada (España), Serv. Publ. Universidad de Granada, 98 pp.
- Rivas-Martínez S (2008) *Global Bioclimatics (Clasificación Bioclimática de la Tierra)*. December I. http://www.globalbioclimatics.org/book/bioc/global_bioclimatics-2008_00.htm
- Rivieccio G, Bagella S, Bazan G, Bonini F, Caria MC, Dagnino G, Mariotti M, Turcato C, Gianguzzi L (2020) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from #16 to #20. *Plant Sociology* 57(2): 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2020572/05>
- Rivieccio G, Aleffi M, Angiolini C, Bagella S, Bazan G, Bonini F, Caria MC, Casavecchia S, Castello M, Dagnino D, de Francesco MC, Farris E, Fanfarillo E, Fiaschi T, Forte L, Gianguzzi L, Landucci F, Maneli F, Mantino F, Mariotti M, Pirone G, Poldini L, Poponessi S, Praleskouskaya S, Stanisci A, Tomaselli V, Tozzi FP, Turcato C, Venanzoni R, Gigante D (2021) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from #26 to #36. *Plant Sociology* 58(2): 77–98. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2021582/07>
- Rivieccio G, Angiolini C, Azzella MM, Bagella S, Bonini F, Cannucci S, Caria MC, Crisafulli A, Di Pietro R, Esposito A, Fanfarillo E, Farris E, Ferri V, Fiaschi T, Forte L, Fortini P, Gianguzzi L, Gigante D, Laface VLA, Maiorca G, Mantino F, Mei G, Minutillo F, Morabito A, Musarella CM, Patera G, Perrino EV, Spampinato G, Stinca A, Tavilla G, Tomaselli V, Tondi G, Wagensommer RP, Bazan G (2022) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from #45 to #59. *Plant Sociology* 59(2): 71–98. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2022592/06>
- Romagnoli M, Moronia S, Recanatesi F, Salvati R, Scarascia Mugnozza G (2018) Climate factors and oak decline based on tree-ring analysis. A case study of peri-urban forest in the Mediterranean area. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 34: 17–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.05.010>
- Saitta A (2015) First record of *Eichleriella leucophaea* (Basidiomycota) from Italy. *Check List* 11(6): 1796. <https://doi.org/10.15560/11.6.1796>
- Schicchi R, Raimondo FM (2007) *I grandi alberi di Sicilia. Azienda Foreste Demaniali della Regione Siciliana (Eds) Palermo, Collana Sicilia Foreste*, 312 pp.
- Schmid H, Helfer W (1999) Die Bedeutung der Naturwaldreservate für den Pilzartenschutz. In: *BuchennaturwaldReservate – unsere Urwälder von morgen*. NUA – Natur- und Umweltschutzakademie des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen (Hrsg.). NUA-Seminarbericht 4: 140–146.
- Scuderi G, Raimondo FM, Ilardi V (1994). La sughera nella vegetazione arborea del Trapanese. *Quaderni di Botanica ambientale e applicata* 3[1992]: 223–233.
- Sérgio C, Casas C, Brugués M, Cros RM (1994) Lista vermelha dos Briófitos de la Península Ibérica. Instituto de Conservação de Natureza. Museu, laboratório e Jardim Botânico, Universidade de Lisboa, 45 pp.
- Sessa E (2015) *Le Tenute Reali dei Borbone in Sicilia*. In: Davi G, Mauro E (Eds) *La Casina Cinese nel regio Parco della Favorita di Palermo*. Centro Regionale per l'Inventario, la Catalogazione e la Documentazione della Regione Siciliana, Palermo, 135–162.
- Sferlazza S, Londi G, La Mela Veca DS, Maetzel FG, Vinciguerra S, Spampinato G (2023) Close-to-Nature Silviculture to Maintain a Relict Population of White Oak on Etna Volcano (Sicily, Italy): Preliminary Results of a Peculiar Case Study. *Plants* 12(10): 2053. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12102053>
- Sitonen J, Ranius T (2015) The importance of veteran trees for saproxylic insects. In: Kirby K, Watkins C (Eds) *Europe's changing woods and forests: from wildwood to managed*

landscapes. CABI, Wallingford (UK), 140–153. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781780643373.0140>

Siracusa G (1998) Vegetazione di forra nel territorio di Sant’Alfio (Etna, Sicilia orientale). *Boll. Acc. Gioenia Sci. Nat.* 30(353): 313–319.

Smith CW, Aptroot A, Coppins BJ, Fletcher A, Gilbert OL, James PW, Wolseley PA [Eds] (2009) *The Lichens of Great Britain and Ireland*. The British Lichen Society, Department of Botany, The Natural History Museum, London, 1046 pp.

Sparacio I, La Mantia T, Colomba MS, Liberto F, Reitano A, Giglio S (2017) Qanat, gebbie and water sources: The last refuge for the malacological freshwater fauna in Palermo (Sicily, Italy). *Biodiversity Journal* 8(1): 279–310.

Sparacio I, Surdo S, Pasta S, Duca RL, La Mantia T (2022) Past and current distribution of *Charaxes jasius jasius* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Lepidoptera Nymphalidae) in Sicily in relation to its host plant, *Arbutus unedo* L. (Ericaceae). *Biodiversity Journal* 14(4): 955–967. <https://doi.org/10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2022.13.4.955.967>

Surano N, Gianguzzi L, Raimondo FM (1996) Carta della vegetazione del promontorio di Monte Pellegrino (Palermo). *Quaderni di Botanica ambientale e applicata* 4 [1993]: 139–144.

Tavilla GM, Angiolini C, Bagella S, Bonini F, Cambria S, Caria MC, Esposito A, Fanfarillo E, Ferri V, Fiaschi T, Gianguzzi L, Giusso del Galdo G, Ilardi V, Mei G, Minissale P, Rivieccio G, Sciandrello S, Stinca A, Bazan G (2021) New national and regional Annex I Habitat records: from #37 to #44. *Plant Sociology* 59(1): 49–66. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2022591/05>

Theurillat JP, Willner W, Fernández-González F, Bültmann H, Čarni A, Gigante D, Mucina L, Weber H (2021) International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature. 4th edn. *Applied Vegetation Science* 24: e12491. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12491>

Tomao A, Bonet JA, Castaño C, de-Miguel S (2020) How does forest management affect fungal diversity and community composition? Current knowledge and future perspectives for the conservation of forest fungi. *Forest Ecology and Management* 457: 117678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2019.117678>

Trinajstić I (1995) Plant geographic division of forest vegetation of Croatia. *Annals of Forestry (Dehra Dun)* 20: 37–66.

Tropea C (1907) Contribuzione alla conoscenza delle arboricole di Sicilia. *Atti dell’Accademia delle Scienze Veneto-Trentino-Istria (Padova)* 4: 53–66.

Turrisi RE, Galletti I, Ilardi V (2002) Contributo alla conoscenza della vegetazione di Cava Randello. *Quaderni di Botanica ambientale applicate* 12[2001]: 117–130.

UNEP, CBD (2001) Status, impacts and trends of alien species that threaten ecosystems, Habitat and Species. *UNEP/CBD/SBSTTA/6/INF/5 Annex II*.

Vacca A, Serra G, Scalenghe R (2018) Vegetation, soils, and humus forms of Sardinian holm oak forests and approximated cross-harmonization of vegetation types, WRB Soil Groups and humus forms in selected Mediterranean ecosystems. *Applied Soil Ecology* 123: 659–663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2017.06.024>

Venturella G, Mazzola P, Raimondo FM (1991) Aspetti distributivi e sinecologici di *Ostrya carpinifolia* Scop. in Sicilia. *Quaderni di Botanica ambientale applicata* 1[1990]: 211–246.

Venturella G, Narcisi V, Li Vigni L, Saitta A, La Rocca S (2001) Mycofloristic investigation in *Ilex* groves in Sicily. II. The Niscemi wood (Favorita Park, Palermo). *Documents Mycologiques* 31(121): 35–48.

Zanella A, Jabiol B, Ponge JF, Sartori G, De Waal R, Van Delft B, Graefe U, Cools N, Katzensteiner K, Hager H, Englisch M (2011) A European morpho-functional classification of humus forms. *Geoderma* 164(3–4): 138–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2011.05.016>

Zimbaro M (2016) Mechanical behaviour of Palermo and Marsala calcarenites (Sicily), Italy. *Engineering Geology* 210: 57–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2016.06.004>

Appendix 1

Table A1. Simplified synoptic table of basiphilous holm oaks described for Sicily (all. *Fraxino orni-Quercion ilicis*): **1** – *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *typicum*, Sicilia, from Brullo and Marcenò (1985), table 2, rels. 1–5 and 8; **2** – *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *arbutetosum unedonis*, Sicilia, from Brullo et al. (2009), table 5a, rels. 7–11; **3** – *Pistacio lentisci-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini*, Palermo Plain, table 4; **4** – *Ampelodesmo mauritanici-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *typicum*, Sicani Mts., from Gianguzzi et al. (2016), table 9, rels. 1–8; **5** – *Ampelodesmo mauritanici-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *viburnetosum tini*, Sicani Mts., from Gianguzzi et al. (2016), table 9, rels. 9–20; **6** – *Rhamno alaterni-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *pistacietosum terebinthi*, Palermo, from Gianguzzi et al. (1996), table 6, rels. 1–12; **7** – *Doronico-Quercetum ilicis*, Iblei Mts., from Costanzo et al. (1998), table 1; **8** – *Doronico-Quercetum ilicis*, Iblei Mts., from Barbagallo et al. (1979), table 1; **9** – *Aceri campestris-Quercetum ilicis* subass. *helleboretosum intermedii*, Palermo, from Marcenò and Ottonello (1991), table 1; **10** – *Ostryo carpinifoliae-Quercetum ilicis*, Sicani Mts., from Venturella et al. (1991), table 3; **11** – *Sorbo torminalis-Quercetum ilicis*, Sicani Mts., from Gianguzzi et al. (2016), table 10, rels. 1–10.

Association number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Number of relevés	6	5	15	8	8	12	6	12	7	7	10
Average number of species per relevé	23,0	17,0	15,1	22,5	23,5	21,6	28,0	32,5	25,4	42,5	25,8
Guide species											
<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	V
Char. association and subassociation											
<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	V	V	V	II	II	.	.	III	.	.	.
<i>Arbutus unedo</i> L.	.	V	II	V	III
<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	.	.	V	.	V
<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	.	I	V	.	.	II	IV	.	II	.	.
<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.	III	.	V	.	.	II	.	III	.	.	.
<i>Ampelodesmos mauritanicus</i> (Poir.) T.Durand & Schinz	I	II	I	V	V	IV	.	.	.	V	III
<i>Erica multiflora</i> L.	.	.	.	II	II
<i>Pulicaria odora</i> (L.) Rchb.	.	.	I	III
<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	.	.	I	II	III	V	II	III	.	.	.

Association number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Number of relevés	6	5	15	8	8	12	6	12	7	7	10
Average number of species per relevé	23,0	17,0	15,1	22,5	23,5	21,6	28,0	32,5	25,4	42,5	25,8
<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	.	.	II	.	.	V	III	III	.	I	.
<i>Celtis australis</i> L.	.	.	II	.	.	III
<i>Rhus coriaria</i> L.	II
<i>Doronicum orientale</i> Hoffm.	V	4	.	.	.
<i>Scutellaria rubicunda</i> Hornem.	III	IV	.	.	.
<i>Aristolochia clusii</i> Lojac.	III	III	.	.	.
<i>Acer campestre</i> L.	III	I	V
<i>Ilex aquifolium</i> L.	IV	.	.
<i>Helleborus viridis</i> L. subsp. <i>bocconei</i> (Ten.) Peruzzi	IV	.	.
* <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> Scop.	II	V	.
<i>Euphorbia meuselii</i> Geltman	V
<i>Sorbus torminalis</i> (L.) Crantz	IV
Char. all. Fraxino-Quercion ilicis (*) and ord. Quercetalia ilicis											
* <i>Dioscorea communis</i> (L.) Caddick & Wilkin	II	IV	II	IV	V	IV	V	V	V	IV	V
<i>Rosa sempervirens</i> L.	I	II	II	II	III	II	IV	III	III	III	II
<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> L.	V	.	II	V	IV	II	V	V	V	V	V
* <i>Cyclamen repandum</i> Sm.	I	II	.	II	III	II	IV	V	IV	III	V
* <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.	II	.	III	V	IV	V	III	.	I	.	V
* <i>Cyclamen hederifolium</i> Aiton	.	.	I	V	V	.	II	II	IV	.	II
* <i>Cistus creticus</i> L. subsp. <i>eriocephalus</i> (Viv.) Greuter & Burdet	III	IV	.	II	.	.	I	II	.	.	III
<i>Carex distachya</i> Desf.	II	.	.	.	II	.	III	IV	.	II	II
<i>Viola alba</i> Besser subsp. <i>dehnhardtii</i> (Ten.) W.Becker	I	.	V	II	IV	.	.
<i>Paeonia mascula</i> (L.) Mill.	.	.	.	I	III	.	.	.	III	IV	III
* <i>Emerus major</i> Mill. subsp. <i>emeroides</i> (Boiss. & Spruner) Soldano & F. Conti	.	.	I	V	V	IV	.
<i>Thalictrum calabricum</i> Sprengel	I	.	.	.	I	III	II
* <i>Drymochloa drymeja</i> (Mert. & W.D.J.Koch) Holub subsp. <i>exaltata</i> (C.Presl) Foggi & Signorini	.	.	.	I	V	III
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L.	.	.	I
Char. Cl. Quercetea ilicis											
<i>Rubia peregrina</i> L.	III	IV	III	III	III	V	V	V	V	V	V
<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	V	II	IV	V	V	V	V	V	III	V	V
<i>Hedera helix</i> L.	II	.	II	V	IV	II	V	IV	V	V	V
<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	I	.	II	V	V	V	V	IV	II	II	III
<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> O. Targ.Tozz	V	V	V	III	II	V	III	II	.	.	I
<i>Euphorbia characias</i> L.	I	I	.	III	.	II	III	IV	II	IV	II
<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	I	.	I	V	V	V	V	III	II	.	IV
<i>Teucrium flavum</i> L.	.	II	.	II	II	IV	I	II	.	IV	II
<i>Osyris alba</i> L.	III	.	.	II	III	I	II	III	.	.	II
<i>Lonicera etrusca</i> Santi	III	I	.	I	II	III	V
<i>Stachys majus</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	V	I	II	II	.	V	I
<i>Lonicera implexa</i> Aiton	V	III	.	V	II	II	.
<i>Daphne gnidium</i> L.	II	IV	.	I	.	I	.	II	.	.	.
<i>Dryopteris pallida</i>	I	II	III	III	V	.
<i>Asplenium onopteris</i> L.	II	III	IV	III	I
<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i> L.	I	II	.	.	.	I
<i>Olea europaea</i> L. var. <i>sylvestris</i> (Mill.) Lehr	III
<i>Anagyris foetida</i> L.	.	.	I
<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> L.	.	.	I
Other species											
<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i> Schott.	II	II	I	I	III	III	IV	II	II	IV	III
<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.	II	II	V	I	III	III	III	II	.	V	I
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq.	III	.	.	IV	IV	II	V	IV	I	.	IV
<i>Quercus pubescens</i> Willd. s.l. [sub <i>Q. virgiliana</i> (Ten.) Ten.] [see Di Pietro et al. 2020, 2021]	.	.	.	V	V	I	V	V	.	V	IV
<i>Clematis vitalba</i> L.	.	.	.	IV	III	.	II	II	III	IV	III
<i>Brachypodium sylvaticum</i> (Huds.) P.Beauv.	.	.	.	V	IV	.	V	II	IV	III	V
<i>Prunus spinosa</i> L.	.	.	.	I	III	I	.	.	III	III	III
<i>Rosa canina</i> L.	.	.	.	I	I	IV	II
<i>Daphne laureola</i> L.	II	V	III

Table A2. Simplified synoptic table of the Sicilian associations pertaining to the alliance *Oleo sylvestris-Ceratonion siliquae* (the values in cells refer to characteristic or differential species, while the symbol (*) points out the dominant species of the association). Associations corresponding to the numeric codes: 1 – *Rhamno alaterni-Euphorbietum dendroidis* subass. *typicum*, from Brullo and Marcenò (1985), table 19 (sub *Oleo-Euphorbietum dendroidis*); 2 – *Rhamno alaterni-Euphorbietum dendroidis* subass. *phlomidetosum fruticosae*, Brullo and Marcenò (1985), table 20, rels. 1–6; 3 – *Rhamno alaterni-Euphorbietum dendroidis* subass. *euphorbietosum bivonae*, from Gianguzzi and La Mantia (2008), table 11; 4 – *Rhamno alaterni-Euphorbietum dendroidis* subass. *rhamnetosum oleoidis*, from Brullo et al. (2009) table 3b, col. 17–19; 5 – *Pistacio lentisci-Chamaeropetum humilis*, from Brullo and Marcenò (1985), table 22; 6 – *Pistacio terebinthi-Celtidetum aetnensis* subass. *typicum*, from Gianguzzi et al. (2014a, 2014b), table 2, rels. 1–14; 7 – *Sarcopoterio spinosi-Chamaeropetum humilis*, from Bartolo et al. (1982), table 29 (sub *Chamaeropo humilis-Sarcopoterietum spinosi*); 8 – *Teucrio fruticantis-Rhamnetum alaterni*, from Turrisi et al. (2002), table 8; 9 – *Myrto communis-Pistacietum lentisci*, from Bartolo et al. (1982), table 28; 10 – *Ephedro fragilis-Lycietum europaei*, from Brullo and Marcenò (1985), table 24; 11 – *Asparago acutifolii-Ziziphietum loti*, from Gianguzzi et al. (1996), table 4; 12 – *Chamaeropo humilis-Quercetum calliprini*, from Brullo et al. (2009), table 3c, rels. 16–20; 13 – *Pyro amygdaliformis-Calicotometum infestae*, from Gianguzzi and La Mantia (2008), table 12; 14 – *Salvio fruticosae-Phlomidetum fruticosae*, from Barbagallo et al. (1979), table 2, rels. 1–12; 15 – *Ampelodesmo-Juniperetum turbinatae* subass. *cistetosum creticae*, from Gianguzzi et al. (2012) table 7; 16 – *Ruto chalepensis-Oleetum sylvestris*, from Gianguzzi and Bazan (2020a), table S1; 17 – *Chamaeropo humilis-Oleetum sylvestris* subass. *acanthetosum mollidis*, from Gianguzzi and Bazan (2020a), table S4; 18 – *Asparago albi-Artemisietum arborescentis*, from Gianguzzi et al. (2016), table 6; 19 – *Euphorbio characiae-Anagyridetum foetidae*, from Gianguzzi et al. (2016), table 7; 20 – *Hippocrepido emeri-Bupleuretum fruticosi*, from Brullo et al. (1993), table 3; 21 – *Spartio juncei-Bupleuretum fruticosi*, from Raimondo and Iardi (2009); 22 – *Malvo olbiae-Ptilostemonetum greuteri*, from Gianguzzi et al. (2022), table 1; 23 – *Viburno tini-Phillyreum latifoliae* ass. nova, table 5; 24 – *Teucrio flavi-Phillyreum latifoliae* ass. nova, table 7.

Association number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
Number of releves	20	6	8	3	20	14	9	8	13	6	6	5	8	12	9	12	28	8	10	6	24	12	12	10	
Average number of species per relevé	17,5	15,8	24,1	18,6	15,3	23,5	30,0	15,5	30,8	18,0	21,0	13,6	15,4	29,3	14,8	21,7	18,5	13,5	15,3	22,2	14,9	30,0	12,6	14,9	
Char. of association and subassociation																									
<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i> L.	V*	V*	V*	V*	I	II								III	V	II	V	I	IV						V
<i>Phlomis fruticosa</i> L.		V												V*					II						
<i>Euphorbia bivonae</i> Steud.			V																				III		
<i>Ephedra major</i> Host			II																						
<i>Rhamnus lycioides</i> L. subsp. <i>oleoides</i> (L.) Jahand. & Maire				V	I													II							
<i>Celtis tournefortii</i> Lam. subsp. <i>aetnensis</i> (Tornab.) Raimondo & Schicchi						V*																			
<i>Poterium spinosum</i> L.							V*								II										
<i>Myrtus communis</i> L.	II								V	II															
<i>Ephedra fragilis</i> Desf.		II						III	V	V															
<i>Lycium europaeum</i> L.										V*															
<i>Ziziphus lotus</i> (L.) Lam.											V*														
<i>Quercus coccifera</i> L.												V*													
<i>Pyrus spinosa</i> Forssk.		I				II							V	I						I					
<i>Salvia fruticosa</i> Mill. subsp. <i>thomasii</i> (Lac.) Brullo, Gugl., Pav. & Terr.														V											
<i>Juniperus turbinata</i> Guss.																V*									
<i>Erica multiflora</i> L.																V									
<i>Cistus creticus</i> L. subsp. <i>creticus</i>																V									
<i>Acanthus mollis</i> L.					III									III			V	I		V	I	IV	IV	V	
<i>Artemisia arborescens</i> (Vaill.) L.	II		I	I	I					II						III	II	V*			I				
<i>Anagyris foetida</i> L.	I		I	I												II	III		V*						
<i>Emerus major</i> Mill. subsp. <i>emeroides</i> (Boiss. & Spruner)	I														I	I	I			V	IV	III			
Soldano & F. Conti																					V*	V*			
<i>Bupleurum fruticosum</i> L.																					V*	V*			
<i>Spartium junceum</i> L.																						IV			
<i>Ptilostemon greuteri</i> Raimondo & Domina																							V*		
<i>Malva olbia</i> (L.) Alef.																							V	V	
<i>Centranthus ruber</i> (L.) DC.																								V	
<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.																								V	
<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i> (L.) Druce																								IV	
<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i> L.			I	III	I	I	II		IV			V		I	V	II	I					II	V	V	

Association number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
Number of relevés	20	6	8	3	20	14	9	8	13	6	6	5	8	12	9	12	28	8	10	6	24	12	12	10	
Average number of species per relevé	17,5	15,8	24,1	18,6	15,3	23,5	30,0	15,5	30,8	18,0	21,0	13,6	15,4	29,3	14,8	21,7	18,5	13,5	15,3	22,2	14,9	30,0	12,6	14,9	
Char. alliance <i>Oleo-Ceratonion siliquae</i>																									
<i>Olea europaea</i> L. var. <i>sylvestris</i> (Mill.) Lehr.	IV	II	V	V	III	I	II	II	IV	III	II	I	I	IV	IV	V*	V*	.	I	.	II	.	.	V	.
<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> L.	III	II	V	I	V*	.	V*	II	V	IV	.	IV	I	II	.	I	V	I	I	.	.	IV	.	.	.
<i>Teucrium flavum</i> L.	II	I	.	.	.	I	III	III	II	I	.	.	IV	I	V	.	V	.
<i>Asparagus horridus</i> L.	III	I	.	II
Char. ord. <i>Pistacio-Rhamnetalia alaterni</i>																									
<i>Stachys major</i> (L.) Bartolucci & Peruzzi	IV	V	V	V	III	II	IV	V	IV	IV	.	III	III	V	IV	V	IV	III	III	I	I	III	IV	III	.
<i>Teucrium fruticans</i> L.	IV	II	II	III	IV	.	IV	V	V	.	II	I	V	.	III	III	.	.	I	II	II
<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L.	III	.	II	V	V*	.	III	V	V*	IV	.	II	I	IV	V	IV	V	.	.	.	III	I	V	V	.
<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.	II	IV	IV	.	II	.	.	V	.	.	I	.	.	IV	IV	IV	III	.	IV	.	III	II	II	.	.
<i>Asparagus albus</i> L.	I	I	V	.	III	.	III	.	IV	I	.	IV	III	.	III	IV	V	IV
<i>Osyris alba</i> L.	I	III	I	.	.	II	.	.	.	III	I	.	.	IV	.	II	III	II	III	I	II
<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i> L.	.	II	I	.	.	V	I	.	.	IV	I	III	I	.	I	.	.	V	III	V	.
<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	.	.	II	.	.	III	I	.	III	II	I	.	.	I	III	V	V	.
<i>Ceratonion siliqua</i> L.	III	.	.	.	II	.	.	I	I	III	.	II	I	III
Char. Cl. <i>Quercetea ilicis</i>																									
<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	IV	IV	V	V	IV	V	V	V	V	V	IV	V	IV	V	IV	V	V	II	V	V	IV	IV	III	III	.
<i>Rubia peregrina</i> L.	II	.	V	II	III	IV	.	III	IV	V	IV	III	IV	III	I	IV	IV	I	III	V	V	V	I	IV	.
<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	II	.	II	.	III	III	.	II	IV	V	II	IV	II	II	.	IV	IV	.	II	III	III	V	III	.	.
<i>Arisarum vulgare</i> Targ. Tozz.	II	IV	I	II	II	.	IV	IV	II	V	V	II	IV	.	.	V	V	.	IV	III	I	III	IV	IV	.
<i>Cytisus infestus</i> (C. Presl) Guss.	IV	II	IV	.	V	.	IV	.	III	IV	.	III	V*	V	.	II	II	.	.	III	IV
<i>Ampelodesmos mauritanicus</i> (Poir.) T. Durand & Schinz	IV	I	V	III	III	I	I	.	III	II	V	III	III	II	.	I	V	V	I	.	.
<i>Daphne gnidium</i> L.	II	.	I	I	I	IV	.	.	II	II	.	I	II	IV	.	I	II
<i>Allium subhirsutum</i> L.	I	I	I	II	I	IV	II	.	V	V	.	IV	.	.	II	II	.	.
<i>Dioscorea communis</i> (L.) Caddick & Wilkin	I	II	I	.	.	III	II	I	.	.	II	I	III	III	I	.
<i>Ruta chalepensis</i> L.	I	.	IV	IV	.	V	I	.	V	V	.	III	I	III	IV	I	.
<i>Rosa sempervirens</i> L.	II	I	.	.	II	I	I	III	III	III	II	I	I	.
<i>Euphorbia characias</i> L.	V	I	.	I	I	.	V	II	I	I
<i>Lonicera implexa</i> Aiton	I	II	.	I	III	.	.	II	.	.	I	.	.	.	II	.	.	III	.	.	.
<i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.	I	I	I	III	II	III	III	.	.
<i>Cyclamen hederifolium</i> Aiton	.	.	IV	.	.	IV	I	II	I	.	.	II	II	.	III	.	.	.
<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	I	II	.	.	I	IV	I	III	V	V	.
<i>Cyclamen repandum</i> Sm.	I	.	.	I	.	IV	I	.	.	.	III	I

Table A3. List of old-growth trees and shrubs recorded in Bosco Niscemi and in closely adjacent areas.

N°	Species	Height (m)	Coordinates	Maximum circumference at the stump (m)	Circumference 1.3 m above the ground	Canopy width (m)	Estimated age (years)	Conditions of the plant
1	<i>Ulmus minor</i>	14.00	38°09'31"N, 13°20'20"E	1.95	1.16	14.0 N-S 9.5 E-W	80/100	Discreet; some dry branches
2	<i>Ulmus minor</i>	12.00	38°09'32"N, 13°20'24"E	1.80	1.52	12.0 N-S 9.0 E-W	80/100	Senescent; several dry branches
3	<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i>	10.50	38°09'38"N, 13°20'21"E	1.91	1.10 (1+3)	9.5 N-S 6.5 E-W	80/100	Good
4	<i>Albizia julibrissin</i>	6.50	38°09'42"N, 13°20'21"E	1.26	1.13	8.0 N-S 4.0 E-W	220	Senescent; several dry branches
5	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	25.00	38°09'48"N, 13°20'20"E	3.75	2.81	14.0 N-S 12.0 E-W	220	Good
6	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	6.50	38°09'43"N, 13°20'20"E	2.26	0.63	7.0 N-S 12.0 E-W	150	Good; coppiced trunk
7	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	22.00	38°09'45"N, 13°20'20"E	4.58 (many stems)	2.21 (one)	24.0 N-S 22.0 E-W	220	Senescent; several dry branches
8	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>	3.00	38°09'44"N, 13°20'20"E	2.25	0.70	8.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	200	Discreet; curved trunk
9	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	9.50	38°09'45"N, 13°20'20"E	1.30	0.70	8.0 N-S 6.5 E-W	160	Good
10	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	7.50	38°09'46"N, 13°20'19"E	1.95	0.49	7.5 N-S 6.0 E-W	180	Good; coppiced trunk
11	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	8.00	38°09'46"N, 13°20'18"E	2.95	0.67	8.0 N-S 9.0 E-W	180	Good
12	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	9.50	38°09'42"N, 13°20'12"E	1.38	0.88	7.0 N-S 6.5 E-W	180	Good
13	<i>Ulmus minor</i>	22.00	38°09'31"N, 13°20'25"E	3.55	2.02	25.0 N-S 21.0 E-W	180	Good
14	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	7.00	38°09'37"N, 13°20'10"E	1.96	0.72	5.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	180	Senescent; several dry branches
15	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	8.50	38°09'44"N, 13°20'13"E	2.55	1.00	8.5 N-S 8.0 E-W	180	Good
16	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	8.50	38°09'43"N, 13°20'14"E	2.22	0.88	9.0 N-S 9.0 E-W	180	Good
17	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	12.00	38°09'38"N, 13°20'10"E	4.17	1.13	11.0 N-S 12.0 E-W	200	Senescent
18	<i>Viburnum tinus</i>	5.00	38°09'51"N, 13°20'09"E	0.95	0.17	4.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	100	Good
19	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	13.00	38°09'52"N, 13°20'08"E	2.16	0.93	10.0 N-S 15.0 E-W	200	Good
20	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	8.00	38°09'52"N, 13°20'08"E	3.08	0.93	6.5 N-S 6.0 E-W	200	Good
21	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	20.00	38°09'54"N, 13°20'07"E	3.58	1.14	15.0 N-S 18.0 E-W	220	Senescent
22	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	20.00	38°09'52"N, 13°20'12"E	4.07	2.41	25.0 N-S 21.0 E-W	220	Senescent
23	<i>Celtis australis</i>	12.00	30°09'58"N, 13°19'58"E	3.30	3.22	12.0 N-S 16.0 E-W	220	Senescent
24	<i>Olea europaea</i>	21.00	30°09'57"N, 13°19'58"E	4.22	1.77	25.0 N-S 23.0 E-W	300	Good
25	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	16.00	38°09'57"N, 13°19'55"E	3.11	0.73	15.0 N-S 15.0 E-W	200	Good
26	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	8.00	38°09'36"N, 13°20'22"E	1.35	1.21	10.0 N-S 10.0 E-W	80/100	Good
27	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	17.00	38°09'38"N, 13°20'15"E	4.51	3.01	18.0 N-S 16.0 E-W	220	Good
28	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i> L.	10.00	38°09'38"N, 13°20'10"E	2.25	1.30	8.0 N-S 8.5 E-W	220	Senescent
29	<i>Viburnum tinus</i>	4.00	38°09'40"N, 13°20'12"E	1.09	0.17	4.0 N-S 3.0 E-W	80	Good
30	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	13.00	38°09'42"N, 13°20'13"E	1.10	1.22	10.0 N-S 7.5 E-W	200	Good
31	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	10.00	38°09'45"N, 13°20'12"E	4.88	0.63	9.0 N-S 13.0 E-W	220	Good
32	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	15.00	38°09'57"N, 13°20'06"E	5.34	3.15	15.0 N-S 15.0 E-W	220	Good
33	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	18.00	38°09'52"N, 13°20'07"E	1.80	1.12	8.0 N-S 10.0 E-W	220	Excellent
34	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	14.00	38°09'52"N, 13°20'08"E	1.87	0.87	13.0 N-S 13.0 E-W	220	Excellent
35	<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> (on <i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>)	7.00	38°09'58"N, 13°20'03"E	0.90	0.85	6.0 N-S 5.0 E-W	200	Excellent
36	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>	7.00	38°10'08"N, 13°20'02"E	2.40	0.95	6.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	220	Senescent
37	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	25.00	38°10'06"N, 13°20'06"E	2.87	3.27	10.0 N-S 8.0 E-W	220	Senescent
38	<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	32.00	38°10'05"N, 13°20'07"E	3.45	2.77	25.0 N-S 22.0 E-W	220	Good
39	<i>Celtis australis</i>	28.00	38°10'11"N, 13°20'08"E	4.05	3.01	25.0 N-S 25.0 E-W	200	Good
40	<i>Celtis australis</i>	25.00	38°10'10"N, 13°20'08"E	3.69	2.90	28.0 N-S 25.0 E-W	200	Good
41	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	13.00	38°10'09"N, 13°20'10"E	2.24	0.97	9.0 N-S 7.0 E-W	200	Excellent
42	<i>Celtis australis</i>	22.00	38°10'12"N, 13°20'15"E	3.34	2.56	22.0 N-S 22.0 E-W	200	Good
43	<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i>	14.00	38°10'13"N, 13°20'13"E	4.67	0.73	13.0 N-S 13.0 E-W	200	Good
44	<i>Olea sylvestris</i>	14.00	38°10'12"N, 13°20'16"E	4.30	1.65	15.0 N-S 14.0 E-W	200	Excellent
45	<i>Viburnum tinus</i>	4.00	38°10'14"N, 13°20'16"E	2.44	0.12	3.0 N-S 5.0 E-W	200	Excellent
46	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	5.50	38°09'32"N, 13°20'38"E	2.26	5.00	4.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	200	Good
47	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	6.50	38°09'33"N, 13°20'37"E	3.42	7.50	8.0 N-S 6.0 E-W	200	Good